

NEWBITS

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D4.1 Formalization of NEWBITS modelling method and systemic business dynamics

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Abbreviations

ABM:	Agent Based Modelling
BE:	Business Ecosystems
BM:	Business Model
CAS:	Complex Adaptive Systems
C-ITS / (C-) ITS:	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CPS:	Cyber Physical Systems
CPT:	Cyberise the physical
CS:	Case Studies
EC:	European Commission
EE:	Economic Entities

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EU:	European Union
GA:	Grant Agreement
GIS:	Global Information Systems
GPS:	Global Positioning Systems
H2020:	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
ICT:	Information and Communication Technology
I-S:	Industrial Symbiosis
ISNs:	Industrial Symbiosis Networks
IT:	Information Technologies
ITS:	Intelligent Transport Systems
LSE	London School of Economics
MIT:	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
NO:	Network Orchestrator
OBUs:	On-Board Units
PSS:	Product Service System
RHW:	Road Hazards Warning
RWW:	Road Works Warning
S-D:	Service-Dominant logic
SSS:	Smart Service Systems
TMC:	Traffic Management Centre
VN:	Value Networks
VNA:	Value Network Analysis
V2I:	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2V:	Vehicle to Vehicle
WoM:	Word of Mouth
WP:	Work Package

Abstract

This report includes a literature review focused on value networks and Value Network Analysis (VNA) framework and its application, but also on other key related concepts which can be extrapolated to the ITS domain, such as “business ecosystem”, “network business models”, “smart service systems”, “industrial symbiosis”, “cyber physical systems” and “service dominant logic”. The results of a business research activity covering ITS and C-ITS domains are analysed concluding through a knowledge build up and filtering process in the validation of a tailored made VNA approach for NEWBITS, ensuring that the process is properly designed towards achieving the project objectives, while ensuring the method with theoretical background.

The key outcome for Task 4.1 “Business ecosystem based research” is a comprehensive and validated conceptual and operative framework for the launching of the Value Network Analysis in Task 4.2.

Introduction

The economic and commercial aspects of ITS are examined in WP4 of the NEWBITS project. One of the key elements to support the process of designing a new business model suited for ITS is the theoretical investigation of the state of the art of concepts around business model. The performed research for new business models methodically follow a parallel top-down and bottom-up approach. The outcomes of the theoretical research are presented in this report.

During the proposal stage of the project, acknowledging the experience of the consortium, a set of key concepts have been proposed to be included in the proposed new business model for ITS. The first has been that the new business models will be focused in a networked context and secondly a tailored approach to the Value Network Analysis (VNA) will be developed aiming at generating a comprehensive description of where value lies in a network, and how it is created.

For the networked context NEWBITS examines four (4) ITS case studies that are covering different models of transports; use different ITS technologies and each one satisfy different markets with different business models. The work performed in this deliverable takes into consideration the work performed in WP2 and WP3 of this project and supports the definition of new business models and sets the ground for the creation of a systemic approach for Business Modeling and strategy analysis in ITS domain (WP5).

This report (Deliverable 4.1) is devoted to define and validate the methodological framework in order to deploy the Value Network Analysis (in Task 4.2) based on the outputs generated on WP2 related to the ITS and C-ITS framework and the case studies, and the results from Task 3.1. The following literature review (Section 1) is focused on value networks and VNA framework and its application, but also on other key related concepts which can be extrapolated to the ITS domain, such as “business ecosystem”, “network business models”, “smart service systems”, “industrial symbiosis”, “cyber physical systems” and “service dominant logic”.

In the second section the results of a comprehensive business research activity covering ITS domain are presented. The scope of the business research is to assess other similar integration-based, ecosystem innovations to search and identify possible commonalities at conceptual level that enriches NEWBITS approach. The four case studies are examined and verify how they fit to the examined in Section 1 concepts.

In the third section of this report the outcomes of the literature review as a knowledge build up and filtering process attempts to validate the pre-designed by the consortium VNA approach at proposal stage, ensuring that the process is properly designed towards achieving the project objectives, while ensuring the method with theoretical background.

1. Literature Review

1.1 Business ecosystems

The strategic management literature in recent years focuses on Business Ecosystems (BE) as sources of competitive advantages for the individual firms. Companies co-evolve their skills and roles in a business ecosystem. The idea of business ecosystems is rooted in the value networks theory and is seen as explaining how a group of companies can simultaneously create value by putting together their assets and skills. Rong et al. (2015)¹ sum up the existing literature as studying business ecosystems either as networks of interdependent stakeholders who evolve together and share the same fate, or as established value networks with fixed interconnected roles. In this work, two strands of research have been identified: the first focuses on the roles that construct the ecosystem (Constructive elements) while the second focuses on the interconnection of these roles (Configuration).

Within an ecosystem the entities should both cooperate and compete as demonstrated by Zahra et al (2012). This is considered as a demanding task that requires the co-existence of strategic thinking together with the entrepreneurial operations². These two processes are interacting and feedback each other in a continuous mode. The interactions among the two processes determine the success or failure of a firm in the ecosystem. The interactions differ significantly among different types of identified ecosystems. Clarysse et al (2014) provide evidence that business ecosystems are a non-linear value creation process (often informal horizontal links) as groups of firms that delivers integrated solutions to the end-users³. The non-linearity properties emerge from the complexity of the ecosystem.

There are theoretical works that support that BE could be studied as complex adaptive systems (CAS). These systems typically include multiple loops and multiple feedback paths between many interacting entities, as well as inhibitory connections and preferential reactions (Battistella et al, 2013)⁴. Business ecosystems as paradigms of CAS, change and evolve over time as a result of the interactions between the members of the BE and the interaction between the ecosystem and its everchanging business environment. The complexity of business ecosystems suggests that the emergence and success of ecosystems is a dynamic process requiring a multifaceted responsiveness. As the ecosystem evolves during its life time, and interacts to the external environment, its capabilities define the level of services and the impacts to the society in an adaptive way. This process, leads to adaptations of the cooperative behaviour of the stakeholders too, as the ecosystem reaches higher levels of maturity over time. It is imperative that companies establish a sound measurement approach based on quantitative data, to allow monitoring and assessing the performance of the ecosystem, both from a static and dynamic point of view. This is a prerequisite that allows to optimize the rules governing the ecosystem.

Companies may benefit by their participation in a BE regardless their size. In Europe the business ecosystems tend to follow a less structured model with improved dynamics. This model may incorporate small, medium and large firms. In such a model, all actors may complement each other. This leads to a more dynamic distribution of effort. This type of BE is more appropriate for

the service and the knowledge industries, and allows small firms to redefine their position and role (Nachira et al 2015)⁵.

Advanced business ecosystems models support the engagement of customers and end-users on the demand side of their markets (Wright, 2014)⁶. Therefore, the innovation in business ecosystems does not focus solely on the technology development, but also on the markets or the commercialization of their services. Customers participate in their business ecosystem by forming interest groups or communities. This participation creates social value as well as economic value. By creating social value, firms accumulate social capital within their business ecosystems. Then this accumulated social capital reverts to their performance and competitiveness (Joo et al, 2017)⁷. Customers affect the business ecosystem through positive or negative word-of-mouth (WoM) behaviours. In addition, advances in IT help customers effectively form interest groups, allowing their voice to be heard within business ecosystems. The business ecosystems are operating environments that encourage and enforce the transition from value creation to value co-creation, as they allow to, redefine how stakeholders involve in the value creation process (Leviäkangas et al, 2014)⁸. Value co-creation can be seen as a participatory operation. The literature includes different examples of such operations as Artto et al (2016)⁹ examined a participatory scheme known as the Cuckoo's Nest approach which promotes the idea for collective action which sees primarily the business ecosystem as a whole, instead of promoting the own individual businesses.

Companies cooperate rather than compete to create and deliver solutions that meet the expectations of end-customers (Moore, 1993)¹⁰. For instance, Gawer et al (2002) describe how multinationals in the digital world are able to manage innovation through their business ecosystem as "platform leaders"¹¹. Furthermore, Internet and digitization allow business ecosystems to evolve into digital business ecosystems. Razavi et al (2010)¹² defined the new components of the digital systems. They support a loosely coupled business interaction of firms that maintain the sustainability of their environment. Digital ecosystems are open communities without any centralized control, which provide a range of services that can be composed together to meet the various needs of partners, and consumers.

Two important ingredients of any business ecosystems are: (1) each partner is specialized in a specific activity and it is the collective effort of many actors that constitute value, not the individual effort of a firm (Iansiti et al, 2004)¹³; and (2) there is a need for a "keystone" company, which role is to make sure that each member of the ecosystem remains in good health (Moore, 1993).

Iansiti et al (2004) examine the concept of the keystone strategy. This is a strategy that improves the strength of the entire ecosystem, and then leads to benefit the performance of the firms. The keystones typically occupy richly connected hubs and regulate connections among ecosystem members and work to increase diversity and productivity. There are two fundamental components of an effective keystone strategy: a) to create value within the ecosystem, b) the keystone to share the value within the ecosystem. The behaviour of a community of organisations in a business ecosystem is inextricably intertwined. The performance of any individual organisation is tied to the performance of the whole. Leadership enables ecosystem firms to invest in a shared future and common goals bind the ecosystem members together.

A number of the principles of business ecosystems are applicable to the NEWBITS Case Studies and considered supporting towards the design of a new business model for (C-) ITS solutions. The described networks under the frame of the CS appear dependent on the different tangible and intangible resources possessed by their stakeholders. In the CS the stakeholders coexist both competing and with complementing functions under a business ecosystem defined by each case study. The presentation of the CS does not clearly verify how the emerging networks are coordinated and orchestrated while a lead member entity is not identified. This role is considered that could be identified after the implementation of the proposed tailored made VNA. NEWBITS Case Studies involve a number of stakeholders that play different key roles in the respective ecosystems, based on their specific and unique capacities. The overall orientation of the CS to setup business ecosystems in the ITS/C-ITS sector, which will be able to adapt their operation under changing external conditions, through the initiation of new activities when needed, in order to maintain their sustainability through uninterrupted value-creation over time can be considered a viable assumption.

1.2 Network Business Models

Globally we are facing a new era, as networking and connectivity is not a trend any more but sweeping through many fields. Mainly, the terms are being correlated to ICT and the web, but they play a crucial role in our physical, business and social environments. On the other hand, companies are struggling for continuous innovation in order to gain competitiveness and thus re-thinking of or re-designing their business model.

In the extended review of more than 100 articles by Boons et al (2013)¹⁴, it is presented that several scholars identify four elements of a business model concept: **i) value proposition, ii) supply chain, iii) customer interface and iv) financial model**. Apparently, two of these elements are relevant with a company's relationships (suppliers and customers). As focusing in sustainable innovation, the authors conclude that even in this domain the networks not only with other firms but with other stakeholders from a broad societal system are crucial for a sustainable development process.

In this context, according to the IBM global CEO study (2006)¹⁵, any innovation introduced to business models should interfere with the organisational structure and mostly with changes in the networking activities (e.g. joint ventures, outsourcing, spin-offs etc.)

As the concept of business model innovation is not widely researched and mainly focused on individual enterprises, Lindgren et al (2010) addressed the challenge of its transformation to a network based one. They formalised and studied three networks of small and medium sized enterprises in the Danish-Norwegian area which include an intelligent utility platform for homes, a high- speed and low-cost ferry, and an open innovation platform for the construction industry. Although, this concept encompasses certain difficulties and challenges, as collaboration among partners, agreement on common values and comprehension of the new business model, the findings are positive and encouraging. It seems that individual companies lacking competencies can access innovation with strategic partnerships. Being part of a network means that incremental

changes in one partner's technologies or systems or products/services can have radical innovative effect in the network as a whole. Additionally, the level of innovation with a networked based business model can be potentially higher as the number and variety of available technologies, ideas, markets is much higher.

By utilising the MIT methodology for telecoms, Eaton et al (2010)¹⁶ define *control points and triggers* in a business model. They first identify the value chains within a particular industry for a product or service, and then build up taxonomy of control points through interviews with relevant experts. Then they illustrate the parties that hold control over these points and examine their economic power. Finally, they establish scenarios of “constellations” of control points to represent each of the major different ways that control can be exerted, and this effectively generates different potential business models.

Briefly the MIT methodology for telecoms focuses on *trigger points* which are those external factors that force a transition from one “constellation” of control points (or business model) to another. It is important to understand triggers such as technological, social, business, regulatory external factors that lead to the evolution of business models. While this methodology focuses on value chains, the authors found it to be suboptimal for the telecom industry and modified the analysis of control points on *value networks*. In addition, they examined business models that extend across an industry rather than on one particular company and provided two examples: Apple's iPhone business model and Google's Android business model. They concluded that while Google pursues a growth strategy in terms of attracting as many end-users to the platform, offering them choice and price options, Apple's strategy focuses on maintaining high margins from sales of a value proposition based on quality.

Moreover, this methodology of control points, being used to analyse value networks, has been successfully transposed from its technical origins to become a socio-technical model by Elaluf-Calderwood et al (2011)¹⁷. By including in the analysis the multiple relationships and flows, conflicts, tussles and ambiguity between stakeholders, control points become a tool that addresses the complexities related to the development of digital infrastructure design. They have pointed out that despite all progress collaboration and resource sharing across networks is still at the beginning of its development. There are many open questions on how can control points be used to enhance the design and innovation of cooperative networks and on how can the concept of control points provide a framework for business value networks.

Anna Wulf and Lynne Butel (2017)¹⁸, have shown that the importance of collaboration between companies, being and acting together in a network, in order to develop competitive advantage and innovative ideas is high and vital. They demonstrated that innovative strategic decisions and business models making, could be easily accelerated within a broader and more diverse business ecosystem. They accepted that networks are a very good basis for the development of business models and they concluded that the business ecosystems offer a broader approach to understanding business network structures and potential innovative strategies and business models. At the same time the results of their research also show that small working groups and networks best facilitate trust and knowledge sharing, which are essential to the development of business models.

In their work Varamaki and Vesalainen (2003)¹⁹ have distinguished different types of multilateral co-operation among SMEs relatively to the intensity of the co-operation, which are: Development circle, Loose co-operative circle, Project group, Joint venture and Joint unit. They have concluded that one co-operation leads to another. It is most probable that an enterprise joins another network as well after getting involved once.

However, the extensive existing literature on the formalisation of business networks, their characteristics and advantages, there is not much research in measuring contribution and benefits of these networks although it is essential for defining their success. In this aspect, Parung and Bitici (2008)²⁰ are applying a model with three kinds of measurements: 1) Input to the collaboration, meaning how strong the contribution of each partner is, 2) Health of the collaboration taking into account five attributes (commitment, co-ordination, trust, communication quality & participation, conflict resolution technique), and 3) Outcomes of the collaboration (performance measurement based on mathematical model).

Finalising the relevant research, we may conclude that: “value lies in the network”. The success of the new emerging platform or network based companies, like Airbnb, Amazon, Netflix and many more, making their competitors envy or even desperate, is the tangible proof. Libert et al (2014)²¹, in collaboration with Deloitte, identified four types of Business Models, based on an examination of 40 years of financial data for the Standard & Poor’s 500 companies:

- **Asset Builders:** Companies that build, develop, and lease physical assets to make, market, distribute and sell physical things (e.g. Ford and Wal-Mart)
- **Service Providers:** Companies which hire employees for providing services to customers or producing billable hours for which they charge. (e.g. Accenture and JP Morgan)
- **Technology Creators:** They develop and sell intellectual property such as software, analytics, pharmaceuticals and biotechnology (e.g. Microsoft and Oracle).
- **Network Orchestrators.** Companies that create a network of peers in which the participants interact and share in the value creation. They sell products /services, build relationships, share advice, collaborate, co-create and more (e.g. eBay, Red Hat, Visa, Uber, TripAdvisor, and Alibaba).

The data analysis demonstrates that the NO ones are valued much higher, 2 or 3 times on average, than companies with other business models and that this gap is widening over time. Why then are just a few companies follow the NO model? According to the authors, mainly, people are intimidated by changes, changing their business model means changes in capital allocation. Also, the new models require new technologies and competencies which are focused on handling intangible assets like knowledge, relationships, other people’s assets and more. as traditional business deals with own physical assets and people. Every company has networks that should activate and exploit for more value and better performance.

In a more recent article, Bonchek and Libert (2017)²² urge traditional businesses to change the way of thinking and suggest that it is not so difficult to acquire the success of the network based companies. As value lies in the different connections and not in single items, companies can take advantage of the different potential connections among their different types of capital (human, financial, intellectual, physical and relational) and incorporate them in their strategy.

In the four examined case studies the stakeholders have created some form of a business network. In this section it has been verified that business networks are key to companies to satisfy their customers' needs and produce innovative product and services. There are challenges both in the ways that business networks are structured and how their value proposition is accumulated. The proposed tailored made VNA, as it is justified in following section will verify the ultimate way that new proposed NEWBITS business model will be designed upon the utilisation of the network business models in the four case studies.

1.3 Smart Service Systems

In this section smart service systems (SSS) are defined and is attempted to identify their effects onto the provision of services. These systems appear to affect service marketing as well and have a disruptive potential that is explained.

Smart service systems feature capabilities for interacting in real time with their environment and they are embedded in human life (Wuenderlich, 2015)²³. Smart service systems support the collection of real-time data, continuous synchronous and asynchronous communication and interactive feedback. Such systems have different variations based upon the level of autonomous decision making, that they can perform; their visibility and embeddedness in objects and customer lives. Smart service systems include intelligent objects that provide services either individually or in a network. These intelligent objects are self-aware of their own condition and their surroundings. Parameter values regarding those conditions are exchanged through real-time data collection, continuous communication and interactive feedback (Allmendinger and Lombreglia, 2005)²⁴.

The **notion of service** is far beyond the typical, as in recent literature (Katzan, 2008) argues "provision of assistance and expertise through a provider–client interaction to create and capture value in business, education, government, and personal endeavours"²⁵. A service is not considered as the summation of embedding components; rather, the exchanges and relation form a higher-order construct (Barile and Polese, 2010)²⁶. Services thus are acknowledged as an "... interaction between entities in a reticular system ... to improve value co-creation outcomes under a win–win logic inside interrelated processes".

Service systems are described as configurations targeting value co creation between people, technology, value propositions connecting internal and external service systems, and shared information (Spohrer et al, 2007). The above-mentioned elements as an agglomeration via some form of regular interaction or interdependence are considered service systems²⁷.

Smart service systems usually manage assets and goals. This management can either be performed by intelligence that is inherited in the systems or supported by interactive management capable of self-reconfiguration in order to perform enduring behaviour capable of satisfying all the involved participants in time. Smart service systems, key functional requirements are interactions/ exchanges between the entities that are included and may be found in any of these: Intelligent Utility Networks and Metering, Intelligent Transportation, Consumer Driven Supply Chains,

Intelligent Oilfields, Manufacturing Productivity, etc. In this light interactions, ties and experiences among actors represent an important part of smart service systems. Connections and interactions among all involved parties within service exchange, attending technology infrastructure upon which they rely smoothens the communication channel between B2B, B2C/C2B, C2C, B2S/S2B C2S/S2C (where B stands for business, C for Customer, S for Stakeholder) (Gummesson and Polese, 2009)²⁸.

Understanding how Smart Service Systems can be launched to markets, has to be noted that the **service marketing** is not on a product but on interactions in service encounters. Value is not referred to that of goods and services, but to what customers perceive. The value is conceptualized via the customers' framework rather than in the producer's perspective. Customers framework include different components as geographical closeness, technological superiority or affordable price level. The logic of service is to support the customers' value-generating processes.

The **disruptive potential of smart services** highly depends on the digital maturity level of branches as well as characteristics of digital solutions (Freund and Cellary, 2017)²⁹. The challenge is to find appropriate business models and monetize value by analysing, visualising and transferring data into new service concepts. A business model describes the value companies provide to their customers and partners (value proposition), how this value is generated by providing resources and activities (value creation) and how the provided value can be monetized by the company in return (value capture).

In the framework of NEWBITS and the four examined case studies Smart Service Systems appear to be included in all of them. Smart Service Systems, notions appear that should be taken into consideration in the design of the new business model for (C-) ITS applications.

1.4 Industrial Symbiosis (I-S)

Following the analysis of business ecosystems and business networks, performed previously Industrial Symbiosis (I-S) appears that have characteristics that can be used in the process of the definition of the NEWBITS business model. In this section I-S is defined, while through literature review key characteristics are identified that either differentiates or have in common with other notions describing relations between industries.

Industrial Symbiosis (I-S) has been defined as “a physical exchange of materials, energy, water, and/or by-products to promote resource efficiency between traditionally separate industries with the intent of promoting collective competitive advantage” (Chertow, 2000)³⁰. Industrial and regional symbiosis innovatively strengthens the synergies between industries, optimizes the utilization of resources and makes full use of the social function of industries to urban communities through the provision of living necessity (Li et al, 2015)³¹. I-S as inherits geographic proximity as one key characteristic enhances collaboration and possibilities for synergies. In an I-S collectively by the members resources are optimised. This optimisation of resources is achieved by the

exchange of by-products and energy between the actors. The scope is to reduce the total raw material and energy consumption with a waste and emissions reduction. Albino et al (2016), argues that I-S concerns the cooperative exchange of resources through business networks aimed at achieving at the same time economic, environmental, and social advantages (Industrial Symbiosis Networks-ISNs)³². Self-organized ISNs are framed as Complex adaptive systems (CASs) (Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012).

Industrial Symbiosis has appeared as a part of the emerging field of industrial ecology. “Symbiosis” is a Greek originating word, that refers to the relation of two or more species that co-exist and relate in a specific environment for mutual benefit. The species can be unrelated in other circumstances but under specific conditions they relate and co-operate. Taking the “symbiosis” appearing in nature to industrial ecosystems, industrial symbiosis too, consists of place-based exchanges among different entities. The key driving benefit to construct symbiotic exchanges is the economic logic. Firms, in the highly competitive environment that are operating are trying to increase their competitive advantages, through industrial symbiosis, lowering production costs and increasing revenues. Therefore, the first requirement for the establishment of a symbiotic relationship is its economic sustainability for all the firms involved (Albino et al, 2015)³³. Six different business models oriented to industrial symbiosis have been identified: waste exchange, co-product generation, co-product generation destined to the internal consumption, co-product generation from external wastes, online waste exchange platform, IS-based business oriented to product generation.

Chertow and Bocken (2014) investigated how a multi-firm approach, “industrial symbiosis” can serve as a sustainable business model³⁴. Although one company may be able to create industrial symbiosis internally through its own diverse business lines, typically this approach involves collaboration and the synergistic opportunities offered by geographic proximity of a diverse set of business. Key findings address the types of businesses that join symbiotic clusters most regularly, common behavioural hurdles, the role of intermediaries and the longevity of such cooperative approaches.

In NEWBITS the proposed business model will satisfy specific needs of emerged networks of stakeholders described in the four case studies. The solutions / services that are provided by the case studies are mainly intangible. Indeed, the case studies are location based focus. The stakeholders co-exist in geographical proximity i.e. one the key characteristics of I-S appears that is fulfilled. The CS stakeholders have developed relations between them and exchange mainly intangible assets, creating “knowledge flows” for the production of new services and applications. These relations are making them gain competitive advantages, and creates an opportunity for the financial sustainability of them. It is mentioned that one of the characteristics of I-S is the resource optimisation. Each stakeholder holds specific resources that after the symbiosis in the pilots, examined in the case studies, share between the industrial symbiosis. One consideration though can be addressed and that is that the Industrial – Symbiosis according the literature appear focused to tangible assets and resources rather than intangible as the case studies examine. Due the design of the NEWBITS business model is proposed that this consideration to be taken into account.

1.5 Cyber-Physical Systems

Computer science is revolutionizing numerous industries. Recent developments in the ICT domain and relevant technologies, such as 5G networks, nanotechnology, sensors, etc. play key role to the emerging so called fourth industrial revolution. Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) represent a critical pillar of this revolution. Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) incorporate both ICT infrastructure and software (the Cyber part) and hardware devices such as sensors and actuators together with human users (the Physical part) into a unified system that should perform in a reliable, secure and fault tolerant manner in real time. CPS are capable to adapt in a sophisticated and smart way to fulfil varying and changing user needs within an ever-changing environment. The above description implies that CPS represent a vast area of research and development activities which address enormous technological and organisational challenges. The anticipated strong impact of CPS in manufacturing, in interactive service provision, and in almost all human activities sets an additional dimension of diversity from the perspective of wide spectrum of applications. It is apparent that recent literature on CPS is also vast. In an attempt to review the area, it is necessary to focus on findings in the literature that demonstrate the unique and novel characteristics of CPS in comparison to conventional Information Management Systems (IMS). In this section it is attempted to address some of the most critical aspects of CPS related to NEWBITS. Issues on the modelling and designing of CPS; networking; data integration; usability and their features are addressed through a literature review.

Jianjun et al (2013) showed that the approach to **modelling and designing cyber-physical systems** is to “cyberize the physical (CTP), which means wrapping software abstractions around physical subsystems”³⁵. Integrating computing and physical processes has been recognized a challenge for some time, motivating the emergence of hybrid systems theories. Detecting the operation of transportation system in real-time, collecting and processing dynamic data is the foundation of computation, based on traffic model to realize control objectives. According to control requirements, traffic control cyber-physical systems need to acquire the status of road transportation system, the motion parameters and traffic group behaviour and individual behaviour parameters.

The anticipated impact of CPS in manufacturing represents a strong motivation for the manufacturers to make the transition from traditionally produced goods to cyber-physical systems. This task sets an urgent requirement to reinvent their innovation and development processes and take a user-centric engineering approach (*Broy and Schmidt, 2014*). A main feature of CPS is the **need for networking**. Cyber-Physical Systems may reach their full value only when interconnected to a network infrastructure. This is the first requirement and it is fairly straightforward. The second step to a CPS-operated environment is the development of high performance, orchestrated and interoperable dynamic web-based and cloud-based services that will interact securely in real time with numerous and different networked devices. This step corresponds to emerging major challenges in the CPS domain³⁶.

Zhai et al (2007) examined the issue of **data integration** which is central in platforms for ITS. Currently, the way that urban traffic management systems are established is upon on their own data storages (such as database or data files). The key missing element is these data storages are operating in isolation to other systems, lacking data share and exchange. In modern cities

different platforms address mobility issues hence is vital to solve how to share and exchange the data among various transport management systems and how to utilize the data sufficiently and improve the level of urban traffic management. The importance of an Integrated Information Platform (IIP) for ITS, which processes various data from different traffic data sources located in various traffic management systems³⁷ is immense. It can serve as a bridge of data share and exchange among different application systems and data sources, which provides traffic management decision-making support, information service function etc.

In CPS there is a unique need for **improved usability**. This need is critical to the effective and efficient performance of any task. According to Wolf (2009), **it's imperative that engineers obtain both explicit and implicit user feed-back when designing and improving cyber-physical systems**. This can be reached through a user-centric engineering process, consisted of a continuous observation of human–computer interaction and the sophisticated interpretation of the context of use. A specific aspect of usability refers to the challenge of learning how to live with networks' limitations³⁸. While small-scale systems can use specialized real-time networks, national-scale systems will inevitably rely on the Internet for part of their operation. CPSs as a very active and new research field, features a variety of questions that need to be solved, at different layers of the architecture and from different aspects of systems design, to trigger and to ease the integration of the physical and cyber worlds. With cyber-physical systems (CPS), **demands for new functionality features multiply**. For example, active safety options such as adaptive cruise control, brake assist, collision avoidance, lane departure warning, sign detection and traction control are not rare anymore in recently built vehicles. With this trend, embedded real-time systems are indispensable in order to sense the physical environment, process data in real-time, control the actuators in a desirable manner and monitor the timing of the whole execution chain for ensuring safety (Kim et al, 2013)³⁹. **CPS provide a natural framework to address the challenges of the transportation sector, since they integrate the physical, cyber, and human factors in a single framework** (Gokhale et al, 2010)⁴⁰.

In NEWBITS the concept of Cyber-Physical Systems is more relevant to two out of four Case Studies, namely CS1 and CS2. Case Study 1 entitled “University VAOPoint Mobility” aims to increase the average occupation and efficiency of a car pool in a university campus. This will gather data from the dynamic traffic environment of the campus and attempt to provide optimal allocation of vehicle resources in real time. Case Study 2 refers to a “C-ITS system to manage the drivers' behavior crossing traffic lights intersections”. Again, the system will collect real time data from the traffic lights intersections and will provide in real time feedback to improve urban mobility. All typical requirements for CPS are present in both cases: multiple sources of data, intelligent and adaptive feedback to the real world (which includes large numbers of human users), all in a secure, reliable and robust way and of course in real time. We may easily conclude that, the NEWBITS Case Studies 1 and 2 represent excellent test-beds for experimentation with Cyber-Physical Systems in the C-ITS domain.

1.6 Service Dominant (S-D) Logic

Service-dominant (S-D) logic is a conceptual framework proposed by Lusch and Vargo (2004). S-D logic aims to explain value creation as the outcome of exchanges, among various

configurations of actors. It describes service as the core purpose of exchange. S-D Logic offers a means for theoretical understanding of how customers, firms and other market actors co-create value through their service interactions. Following the publication of the initial article of Vargo and Lusch, S-D logic attracted the attention of numerous scholars from a wide spectrum of disciplines, who share a common aim to contribute to the understanding of value co-creation. Through the work of this large number of scholars, S-D logic became a co-created effort and it has been continually extended and elaborated.

The initial article of Vargo and Lusch (2004), described the new service-centred view of S-D logic. According to this view, knowledge is conceived as an operant resource. It is considered as the foundation of competitive advantage and economic growth and it is recognised as the key source of wealth. The components of knowledge are: propositional knowledge, which is referred to as abstract and generalized, and prescriptive knowledge, which is referred to as techniques⁴¹. According to Vargo and Lusch (2004), the new service-centred view can be stated through the following elements:

- 1) Identification or development of core competences which include the fundamental knowledge and skills of an economic entity. These represent potential competitive advantage.
- 2) Identification of other entities that could benefit from these competences. These are the potential customers.
- 3) Cultivation of relationships that involve the customers in developing customized, competitively compelling value propositions to meet specific needs.
- 4) Gauge marketplace feedback by analysing financial performance from exchange. This allows to learn how to improve the firm's offering to customers and improve its performance.

In a later article Lusch et al (2007) describe S-D logic as a collaboration between the firm (and relevant partners) and the customer. This allows a strategic orientation that informs the more tactical "Four Ps." In this context, *products* are viewed in terms of service flows, in which the service is provided directly or indirectly through an object; *promotion* consist of conversation and dialog with the customer; *price* is considered as a value proposition created by both sides of the exchange; and finally *place* is substituted by value networks and processes⁴².

A central issue in the literature of S-D logic is the distinction between "operand" vs "operant" resources. In the literature, developed when the dominant logic of marketing was goods-centric, the consumer was seen as an operand resource – a resource to be acted on. In S-D logic, there is a shift from goods-centric view to service-centric view and a shift from *operand* resources to *operant* resources (Kuzgun and Asugman, 2015). The service in the new logic of marketing is "the application of operant resources (skills and knowledge) for the benefit of another party". The traditional Goods Dominant Logic of competing through "services", viewed services as aids to production of goods, "value added" activities (things done to and in conjunction with "products," or at best, a particular type (intangible) of product. As a result, attention remained focused on products, units of output—what S-D logic classifies as "operand resources" (static, usually tangible, resources that must be acted upon to be useful). In contrast, S-D logic views service (a

process) as the application of operant resources— dynamic resources such as competences (skills and knowledge) that are capable of acting and producing effects in other resources – for the benefit of another party. Service Dominant Logic inverts the role of goods and service by making service superordinant to goods. In S-D logic, service can be provided directly to another entity or network or through goods-appliances. Competition is a function of how one firm provides applied operant resources that meet the needs of the customer relative to another firm providing such applied operant resources. S-D logic designates the value concept as value-in-context. With this context, value is not created solely by the firm, but created with collaboration of the customers during their usage of products and interactions with different actors. The role of the firm is to propose a value proposition via resources such as goods and services, and it is the customer who creates the value through a process over time⁴³.

Lusch and Vargo, after the publication of their initial article, promoted and refined the concept of S-D logic through numerous publications. In Lusch and Vargo (2006) the authors state that, in Service Dominant Logic is important to recognize that there are two components of value co-creation: “co-creation of value” and “co-production”. “Co-creation of value” represents a rather drastic departure from Goods Dominant logic, which views value as something that is added to products in the production process and at point of exchange is captured in value-in-exchange (i.e. price). S-D logic argues that value can only be created with and determined by the user in the ‘consumption’ process and through use or what is referred to as value-in-use. “Co-production” involves the participation in the creation of the core offering itself. It can occur through shared inventiveness, co-design, or shared production of related goods, and can occur with customers and any other partners in the value network⁴⁴.

Karpen et al (2012) examined S-D logic under the framework of strategic orientation. In this work the authors clarify how, an S-D orientation represents a set of strategic capabilities that enable an organization to co-create value in service exchanges with what the S-D logic literature calls “value network partners,” such as customers, intermediaries, suppliers, or employees⁴⁵.

Service Dominant Logic in the context of innovation development process was investigated by Michel et al (2008). The authors present how discontinuous innovations due to technology infusion may serve as a way to create spontaneous delight by delivering on value propositions designed around a customer view. Discontinuous innovation in service provision also might provide an opportunity to reposition strategic alliances into a value constellation⁴⁶. An S-D logic posits that firms do not produce value for, but rather with the customer. The value of a market offering (service, product, idea, promise) cannot be defined by the firm but only by the individual customer. Consequently, the customer is always a co-creator of value. This co-creation of value requires that customers perform three different roles: users, buyers, and payers.

The dynamics of S-D logic for co-creating value in the logistics sector are examined by Yazdanparast et al (2010). In this article, the authors show that logistics, as a domain characterized by frequently changing service offerings, provides a context which fits to and may gain from the S-D logic perspective. In addition being an interesting context in which to explore the process of value creation and service provision from an S-D logic perspective, logistics is also an important context because of the increasing importance placed on logistics service as a

competitive tool. The context of logistics service is dynamic and continually changing and value cannot be created unilaterally in such dynamic contexts. Further, value creation requires a combination of resources. S-D logic perspective suggests that a firm must focus on employing the customer as a resource contributing to the creation of value that in effect makes the customer a co-creator of value⁴⁷.

In the NEWBITS Case Studies (CS) the concept of service as the fundamental basis of exchange, is dominant. The Case Studies foresee complex interactions between the players. The entire suit of interactions refers to services. This implies that S-D logic represents an appropriate framework to analyse the anticipated exchanges, since they are all service-critical.

The Case Studies will use recent developments in ICT to interconnect large number of stakeholders and users into complex constellations that operate within a rapidly changing environment. This implies that the service offerings while be extremely volatile and dynamic. The idea of a concept that interprets the operation of the Case Studies ecosystems, as a world dominated by service exchanges, suggests that S-D logic will find an excellent experimentation field in the NEWBITS CS. In addition, we may state that in the above dynamic and changing environment, S-D logic, can support, the issues related to the concept of “co-creation” of value in an optimal way.

1.7 Value Networks

In recent years, industries such as telecommunications, defense and aeronautics are increasingly run by networks of organizations. In these industries, traditional thinking about value creation through the linear model of the industrial age production no longer applies, as products and services become dematerialized and the value chain itself is no longer having a physical dimension (Alee, 2000; Normann and Ramirez, 1993)⁴⁸. Rather, the participating organizations (upstream suppliers, downstream channels to market and ancillary providers, according to Christensen, 2003) need to collaborate with each other and constantly reconfigure their offering, positioning and relationships, in order to remain competitive and relevant in the market. Most importantly, the effectiveness and the qualities of the collaboration among the participating organizations are a key determinant for value maximization, largely predicting the viability and success of the entire network.

Thus, the concept of Value Networks was introduced in the innovation management literature. De Reuver (2009) **defines** a value network as “*a dynamic network of actors working together to generate customer value and network value by means of a specific service offering, in which tangible and intangible value is exchanged between the actors involved*”⁴⁹. The **primary activities taking place** in value networks include: i) the promotion of the network and management of contracts, ii) the provision of services and iii) operation of a common infrastructure. Interactions between the members of the networks take place simultaneously, not sequentially or cyclically. Activities are pooled and preferably reciprocal. Value is derived from the

services provided by the network, its capacity to provide these services, and services opportunity (Stabell and Fjeldstad, 1998).

The value network has a purpose, which is satisfying the **value proposition to the end consumer**⁵⁰ (Parolini, 1999). Value networks define the value created between the participating businesses and their clients or customers, and between the clients/customers themselves. Firms are considered as intermediaries that bring together customers. Members need to complement each other (Stabell and Fjeldstad, 1998)⁵¹. In essence, the linkage of customers in value networks create value (Parolini, 1999). The focus is not set on each member of the value network (company or the industry), but on the value that is created by itself, where all stakeholders co-produce value (Alee, 2000; Normann and Ramirez, 1993). The **core entities within a value network are the activities** performed by its members (Parolini, 1999). As a result, when new organizations enter existing value networks, they must adapt their business models to conform to the value network (Christensen, 2003)⁵². The value network approach has been used to illustrate and identify the location of economic power within an industry through the introduction of bottlenecks and stopping functions at gates (Ballon, 2009)⁵³.

One of the major novelties of this type of business model lies in that it **introduces intellectual capital and intangibles as a form of value** (Alee, 2000)⁵⁴. In value networks, the knowledge and intangible exchange roles are equally important to tangible assets/deliverables if not more. **“Tangible assets”** are resources that can be converted to financial merits and other capital-based resources (goods, services, revenue) that are owned by the firm. **“Intangible assets”** include relationships, employees know-how and competencies, the effectiveness of the organization’s work groups and structure, the efficiency of the organization’s production and service processes, and the level of trust between the people or organizations forming the relationships. These intangible assets represent value that is not accounted in traditional financial records, such as the sense of community, loyalty of customers, enhancement of the brand - image, or co-branding opportunities.

It also emerges that every value exchange should be supported by a defined **mechanism or medium which** enables the transaction that takes place (Alee, 2000). **Technology** is used primarily as medium for enhancing relationships in space and time (Stabell and Fjeldstad, 1998). **Mechanisms** creating knowledge value include: exchanges of strategic information, planning knowledge, technical know-how, collaborative design, policy development, etc., which flow around and support the core product and service value chain (Alee, 2000).

The literature identifies a series of **strengths and weaknesses of value networks** (Alee, 2000; Stabell and Fjeldstad, 1998). Typical Strengths of value networks are:

- capability for scaling and capacity utilization
- quick identification of network members that do not bring in value and can be excluded
- can be easily tweaked with the insertion of only one, well thought out node, which creates value with positive externalities, i.e. that can be transferred to further transactions with in the network.
- activities are performed simultaneously at multiple levels which infer cost and time savings

- reciprocal interdependence ensures value creation for all
- following a successful rollout (the issue that NEWBITS attempts to address), network members acting as mediators may be in a position to charge for membership, service, and equipment in a potentially long-term operations phase in which contracts, infrastructure and service activities are performed concurrently.
- provides learning and development opportunities (spillovers), leading to paradigm shift and diffusion of standards throughout a specific industry.

Potential weaknesses of value networks are:

- a new service has relatively low value to its first customers (but scaling incurs costs hence can be considered a weakness)
- scaling and capacity utilization incur costs
- failure to synchronize activities may lead to a breakdown of the system
- a lot of effort needs to be put into classification of the activities and organisation, to allow for a better coordination of reciprocity, to allow for the development of customer categories and facilitate matching and monitoring.
- ongoing reconfiguration for the value exchanged is needed. Customers may be willing to pay a premium price for a new service, but as this service reaches an increased number of customers and competitors arise, its perceived value lessens.
- tailored strategies and approaches are needed. For example, initial 'giveaways', premium prices, initial lifting of charges for service or equipment
- individualized targeting is difficult in complex networks. Need to identify target segments that will be approached in a unified way.
- scaling may be impeded by geographical factors
- difficult to implement when common industry standards are missing, because this impedes the identification of measurable inter-network connections.

As a general conclusion, we can argue that the value network model includes flexible, malleable and customizable elements. Flexibility also applies to the relationships between the constituting elements of the network. As a result, the VN approach can be applied on multiple levels: the firm, the industry, and even the whole economy. As it exhibits a high degree of tailoring capabilities, we consider that it can be useful for the purposes of NEWBITS both at macro-level (ITS and C-ITS context and market) and meso-level (4 case studies). Moreover, it foresees an organic growth of value network (self-sustainability) by ensuring value creation for all, which is especially relevant to the aims of NEWBITS.

1.8 Value Network Analysis

One of the aims of NEWBITS project is to define the value channeling among the major stakeholders of four business networks that are identified in the examined case studies. Is considered by identifying the value flows among the networks of the case studies stakeholders will provide key information to define the most appropriate business models for the launch of the

ITS products / services to the market. To support this action in this section and after the performed analysis of different concepts regarding business networks we are trying to present the different Modeling Approaches to Value Networks. This presentation is based upon a literature review and presents some of the considered most critical and relevant to NEWBITS concepts.

Value conversion refers to converting or transforming financial to non-financial value, or adversely, transforming an intangible input or asset into a financial value or asset. When considering value conversion, it is necessary to assess the inputs and outputs for each role in the network to determine whether value conversion opportunities are being overlooked. Considering this capability of value networks, Value Network Analysis (VNA) offers a way to model, analyze, evaluate, and improve the capability of a business to convert tangible and intangible assets into other forms of negotiable value, and to realize greater value for itself (Alee, 2008).

Gordijn et al. (2000)⁵⁵ propose the 'e3-value modeling framework'. In this framework, core entities include actors, value objects (what is being exchanged between actors), value ports (point of connection between actor and outside world), value exchanged (connects to a value port, represents pipe through which a value object could be traded), value interface (group of value ports), value activity (performed by an actor motivated by a potential profit), market segment (clustering of actors that assign economic value to object equally, and is typically used to model an group end-consumer with similar interest). **The major weakness of this modeling framework is the lack of a clear strategic focus, which weakens the framework's ability for prescriptive strategic insights.**

Weigand et al. (2007)⁵⁶ propose the c3-value modeling framework, which can be considered as an extension of the e3-value model geared toward strategic analysis. This framework proposes analyzing strategy along the following three dimensions: customer, capabilities and competition. It is built upon the claim that sustained competitive advantage is gained by owning strategic resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable. Essentially, the transferred value is conceived as dual: a primary value that conveys the intended businesses of an actor and the secondary value that enhances the value delivered by the primary value object. It is a powerful strategic technique, with an important weakness: **it focuses directly on the competitor and the customer, thus neglecting the inter-dependencies inherent in the current global economy and the potential given by the network perspective.**

Biem and Caswell (2008)⁵⁷ use the following two approaches to VNA, to arrive at a new framework for modeling value network of inter-organizational interactions. They propose a set of building blocks elements of the model made of economic entities and offering transfers and describe a methodology that configures a business or organization network based on maximizing the consumption of the common value proposition. They view the value network as a set of Economic Entities (EE) connected through transfer of offerings that yields a structural network whose purpose is to deliver a common value proposition to a specified end consumer or market. Economic entities are the primary building blocks of the model. Economic entities may be firms, business units, or individuals. The economic entity can be viewed through three perspectives: the actor perspective, the capability perspective, and the asset perspective. An end consumer is a special node in the network. It is the "sink" whose role is to consume and appreciate the value

proposition of the overall network. The proposed methodology of strategic analysis includes the following steps:

1. Define a strategic value proposition
2. Specify the offerings each partner in the network can provide
3. Select proper partners based on the evaluation of offerings and determine the links that transfer the offerings.
4. Add value and cost to each offering and analyse the VNA model theoretically or by simulation
5. Steps (3)-(5) may be repeated several times until a satisfactory model is achieved.

Allee's (2008) proposed method for VNA includes two steps. The first step is to Map the Network and the second one is to analyse the value network. This mapping step relies on the following three elements^{58 59}:

1. The “**Roles**” played by individuals, groups or collectives who initiate action, engage in interactions, add value and make decisions.
2. The “**Transactions**”, or activities, originate with one participant and end with another. The arrow is a directional link that represents movement and denotes the direction of what passes between two roles. Solid lines are formal contract exchanges around product and revenue, while the dashed lines depict the intangible flows of market information and benefits.
3. The “**Deliverables**” are the actual “things” that move from one role to another. A deliverable can be physical (e.g. a document or a table) or it can be non-physical (e.g. a message or request that is only delivered verbally). It can also be a specific type of knowledge, expertise, advice, or information about something, or a favour or benefit that is bestowed upon the recipient.

Once all of the critical roles, value exchanges and transactions have been identified then it is possible to analyze the network (second step) by performing the following tasks:

- (1) **Exchange analysis** – What is the overall pattern of exchanges and value creation in the system as a whole? How healthy is the network and how well is it converting value?
- (2) **Impact analysis** – What impact does each value input have on the roles involved in terms of value realization?
- (3) **Value creation analysis** – What is the best way to create, extend, and leverage value, either through adding value, extending value to other roles, or converting one type of value to another?

This method allows to analyze the value created from multiple perspectives, such as time, goals, resources, results, costs or value added by linking the diagram to analysis tables.

In the United Kingdom, other scholars in **Eaton et al (2010)** at the London School of Economics (LSE) used *control points* and *triggers* to identify different model scenarios for the telecoms industry, which research was based on work produced by the Value Chain Dynamics Working Group, part of the MIT Communications Futures Programme⁶⁰.

Sutherland (2003) offered a different model by creating the stakeholder VNA of the US Aeronautics & Astronautics industry by connecting each stakeholder using the inputs identified⁶¹. Each defined input to a stakeholder became an output of the originating stakeholder. Theoretically, the sum of all inputs provides a complete set of the value-delivering interactions within the network. In this value network model, the author identifies *value flows* and *value maps* to indicate the output of one stakeholder as the input to another – this represents the delivery of value within the network. The model consists of a qualitative stakeholder analysis initially and then a quantitative VNA which relies on surveys to define the value interaction and channeling, and consequently validates the major stakeholders' value exchanges through private interviews with experts. The model quantifies the flows by calculating the value scores, which provides a basis for creating simplified stakeholder value maps.

Stakeholder theory attracts attention in academic research too, since maintaining an appropriate balance among stakeholder interests and gaining their support includes potential benefits for the central firm⁶². A stakeholder in project business literature exhibits similar characteristics to the business ecosystem actor as a term of the ecosystem theory.

Thanks to the malleable nature of value networks, the proposed tailored made VNA for NEWBITS can allow for the integration of strong points from the other examined business modelling methods (industrial symbiosis, cyber-physical systems, etc.). VNA appears particularly relevant to NEWBITS because it allows to identify value created from multiple perspectives. It consequently allows to focus on the end consumer as the ultimate recipient of value proposition of the overall network. It also allows the quick identification of network members that do not bring in value and can be excluded, and also allows for the quick identification of easy tweaks with the insertion of only one, well thought out node, which creates value with positive externalities. Moreover, VNA allows for a quantification and monitoring of value proposition, which is especially important in order to arrive to the new proposed business model for (C-) ITS solutions market launch.

And it will also provide practical solutions for the policy-makers that aim to incentivize the ITS industry to achieve a higher economic performance in Europe.

2. Business research – Escalation of the knowledge blocks to NEWBITS Case Studies

2.1 The concept of Business Models in NEWBITS

In NEWBITS, it is highly acknowledged that the successful execution and deployment of ITS innovations involving multiple stakeholders requires efficient cooperation, interacting with each other and feeding each other with knowledge as parts of an interconnected ecosystem. In other words, the deployment of ITS initiatives should be analysed from a business ecosystem viewpoint, rather than an individual organisation perspective. This viewpoint that determines the operational level of NEWBITS is generically based on the business ecosystem scope given by Moore (1993)⁶³ as: *the structure and behaviour of a number of organizations sharing a key platform and the set of relationships (symbiosis) between those actors.*⁶⁴

The project pivots on a feasible parametrisation of key business ecosystems aspects such as the stakeholders and the relationships between them, performance, dynamics and strategies. The conceptualisation of the business ecosystems in NEWBITS is supported by three interrelated elements, as described in previous deliverables of the project: the preselection and validation of case studies; the configuration of Communities of Interest; the deployment of a Networking Platform.

The key outcome of the project is expected to be a formalized value network based business modelling, deployed and validated in the framework of the cases. In this sense, it is of outmost relevance to accurately define the concept of Business Model for NEWBITS moreover considering the lack of a widely accepted definition to the business model construct. As noted by Zott et al (2010)⁶⁵, scholars do not agree on what a business model is, and frequently adopt idiosyncratic definitions that fit the purposes of their studies. Moreover, the business model is often studied without explicitly defining the concept.

The concept definition of Business Model in NEWBITS was not provided in the proposal, but indeed, was pre-determined by the methodology designed to formalize the modelling exercise following a tailored Value Network Analysis as a method to analyse competitive environments and develop network based business models.

During the prior subsections of this document, it has been performed a thorough study of relevant literature on Value Network and other relevant concepts to the ITS domain such as Business Ecosystem, Industrial Symbiosis, Cyber Physical Systems, Service Dominant Logic. Before proceeding to the formalization of the modelling approach, there is the need to consider the definition of the Business Model concept for NEWBITS.

Literature review on BM

To approach the vast literature on business models we engaged with the synthesis work provided by several authors:

Lindgren et al (2010)⁶⁶ state that *some authors took a narrow (e.g., technological/financial) focus, while others adopted a more general perspective. Some have incorporated corporate strategy in*

their BM concept, while others left it out. However, it seems that most (if not all) authors agree that a BM is simply defined by the combination of the two terms ‘business’ and ‘model’.

Morris et al. (2004)⁶⁷ presented an overall view, with a strong focus on an entrepreneurial understanding of BMs. They tried to build what they call ‘a unified perspective of BMs’ derived from various academic studies published since the late 1990s. Based on the findings of their cross-theoretical study, the authors concluded that no single theory could fully explain the value creation potential of a business enterprise. Consequently, it is impossible to identify a holistic building block framework for a generic BM depending merely on one author’s perspective. However, they proposed an interactive framework that includes three specific decision making levels (rules, proprietary and foundation) with respect to six basic ‘decision areas’, namely factors related to services and products, the market, internal capabilities, the competitive strategy, economics and growth/exit.

Similarly, Osterwalder et al (2005)⁶⁸ also developed a framework for BMs. They, too, summed up previous academic work on BMs (Stähler, 2001; Weill and Vitale, 2001; Petrovic et al., 2001; Gordijn, 2002; Afuah and Tucci, 2003; Tapscott et al., 2000; Linder and Cantrell, 2000; Hamel, 2000; Mahadevan, 2000; Chesbrough and Rosenbloom, 2000; Magretta, 2002; Amit and Zott, 2001; Applegate, 2001) and arrived at the nine BM ‘building blocks’ presented in Table 1.

Pillar	BM (the nine building blocks)	Content and description
Product	Value proposition	Gives an overall view of a company’s bundle of products and services.
Customer interface offer value to.	Target customer	Describes the segments of customers a company wants to
	Distribution channel	Describes the various means the company uses to get in touch with its customers.
	Relationship	Explains the kind of links a company establishes between itself and its different customer segments
Infrastructure management	Value configuration	Describes the arrangement of activities and resources.
	Core competency	Outlines the competencies necessary to execute the company’s BM.
	Partner network	Portrays the network of cooperative agreements with other companies necessary to efficiently offer and commercialise value.
Financial aspects	Cost structure	Sums up the monetary consequences of the means. employed in the BM

	Revenue model	Describes the way a company makes money through a variety of revenue flows.
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Table 1 Nine BM building blocks (extracted from Osterwalder et al, 2005)

In Europe, there were two dominant pre-2010 schools; a first stream of literature emerged from the University of Lausanne (Switzerland) and the second from the Netherlands and Belgium. Osterwalder (2004)⁶⁹ representing “the Swiss school” focused on analysing the implications of any business model on a single firm. He deconstructs business models to its elements – a product, customer interface, infrastructure management and financial aspects – to enable a detailed analysis of the company’s impact⁷⁰

In contrast, “the Dutch school” focused on the value creation in the networks of organisations, particularly those engaged in “multi-stakeholder innovation projects in the mobile sector”. Thus, the term of business model, identified by Faber et al (2003) and adopted by Ballon (2009)⁷¹ states: “the way a network of companies intends to create and capture value from the employment of technological opportunities”.

New research on business model and innovation has been performed predominantly by the European and American Business schools in modern days. In Zott and Amit (2007)⁷², they show empirically that the design of the business model is central to value creation.

In the extended review of more than 100 articles by Boons et al (2013)⁷³, it is presented that several scholars identify four elements of a business model concept: i) value proposition, ii) supply chain, iii) customer interface and iv) financial model. As focusing in sustainable innovation, the authors conclude that even in this domain the networks not only with other firms but with other stakeholders from a broad societal system are crucial for a sustainable development process. In this context, according to the IBM global CEO study (2006)⁷⁴, any innovation introduced to business models should interfere with the organisational structure and mostly with changes in the networking activities (e.g. joint ventures, outsourcing, spin-offs etc.).

NEWBITS BM Definition

NEWBITS BM approach is employed to gain understanding of how value is created by a number of actors in specific value networks over a time period. Due to the complex nature of ITS-markets and technological innovations, a stakeholder from the network may not have all the capabilities required to offer value-added services or at least, to do so autonomously in order to reach the market. In consequence, actors usually face a challenge of how to integrate into a cluster of actors for creating and delivering value to the customers, and also manage to understand the perceptions of customers/users of such value. Therefore, the consideration of the network as a key unit of analysis, over the firm or enterprise, is essential in NEWBITS business modelling approach.

While it is understood and acknowledged conceptually the need for cooperation and collaboration within a business ecosystem, it is also regarded the high level of complexity to construct business

models for pragmatic purposes on transnational and multi-stakeholder levels. It is even more complex to extract functional recommendations for decision makers based on such models.

In this sense, NEWBITS adopts a dual approach:

At a basic operational level, it is aligned with the scholars that refer to the business model as a “conceptual tool” (Osterwalder, 2004; Teece, 2010). At a more transversal level, the need to acknowledge the BM as a value creation and capture construct is inherent in NEWBITS, thus is aligned with a definition as a “structural template” (Amit & Zoot, 2001). As a result, we consider NEWBITS BM definition in dual approach: operational and conceptual, as a flexible combination of prior definitions provided in the literature:

“A business model articulates the logic, the data and other evidence that support a value proposition to the customer, and a viable structure of revenues and costs for the enterprise delivering that value” (Teece, 2010)⁷⁵.

This definition at operational level is adopted without its inherent focus on the firm or singular enterprise, as it enables the use of business model tools such as business model canvas (or its lean version) as back-up highly functional tool to compose value propositions in complex networks.

In addition, NEWBITS also considers the conceptual layer:

“The business model depicts the content, structure and governance of transactions designed so as to create value through the exploitation of business opportunities” (Amit & Zott, 2001)⁷⁶

Therefore, NEWBITS BM aligns with a contextual approach that considers the value generation (and furthermore, network value generation) itself the key consideration.

2.2 Escalation of the knowledge blocks to NEWBITS Case Studies

This research performed in the framework of the NEWBITS project is based on a case study approach (Eisenhardt, 1989; Yin, 2013). The first case study (CS1) aims to increase the average occupation and achieving a rational use of cars in a university environment with high levels of daily influx of private vehicles. It offers an intelligent carpooling service for daily mobility to the campus, where members of the university community can access numerous carpooling offers. In addition to traditional cost savings on sharing transportation expenses, VaoPoint, as the case study is called, promotes the reduction of users’ carbon footprint and decrease traffic congestion by promoting high-occupancy vehicles. CS1 objectives rely mainly on three aspects: i) Efficiency: Matching users to vehicles and minimising as much as possible trajectory deviations; ii) Comfort: Encourage social preferences matching of users, avoid campus pathway bottlenecks and guarantee access to parking area; iii) Environmental issues: Reduce the carbon footprint (CO₂) and pollution as a result of the reduction in the number of cars used. CS1 proposes a differential innovation, since it introduces a new service in an existing market that can reduce the flow of vehicles into the university campus, but also can be applied to other transit scenarios with similar problems outside of the University such as interurban mobility and industrial parks.

CS2 refers to the C-ITS applications implemented in the past few years in the city of Verona, with particular reference to the activities of the EC (European Commission) Compass4D project. The case-study objectives rely mainly on three aspects: safety, efficiency (energy, level of service) and environmental issues (reducing CO2 and pollutant). These objectives are intended to be pursued by improving the urban traffic performances, through improving driving behaviours and control systems, thanks to the specific cooperative-ITS system implementation. Due to Compass4D implementations, new services have been provided to users: Speed Advisor System (GLOSA system), Road Hazard Warning (RHW) service, Road Works Warning (RWW), and Red light violation function. Also included in the service bundle is the implementation of TSP (Transit Signal Priority) service.

The subject of CS3 is a project called “Synchro-modal container transport corridor Rotterdam-Limburg”. Synchromodality refers to the possibility of choosing the most optimal transport modality at transshipment points. The main objective of the project is to give good insight in the status of containers from sea to warehouses in the hinterland. This allows to: i) Reduce slack in the planning; often containers remain on the terminals longer than necessary due to lack of information. The ambition is to reduce the maximum transport time from 10 to 6/7 days, ii) Improve transport operation: by optimally plan resources and work teams, providing accurate and reliable delivery times and reduction of unreliable and long waiting times at terminals, and iii) Reduce ad-hoc communication between different parties in the supply chain. The service is currently in the pilot phase, with a terminal operator, a warehouse operator and a shipper as pilot customers. At this stage of the development the question arising is which type of stakeholder is going to exploit the service and which (type of) customers are going to take the product.

This case study CS4 “KEEP SAFE” addresses the need to use experts’ knowledge when analysing data to inform decision making in the railway industry. In particular, the case study uses data and experts’ knowledge to serve three overarching purposes within the British railway industry: i) Infrastructure management: Fault prognostics and predictive maintenance; ii) Customer safety: Reducing the risk of accidents due to system failures; iii) Business performance: Reducing disruptions caused by unplanned maintenance and repairs. The case study is currently being implemented with an ultimate aim to deliver a system which allows railway infrastructure owners to collect raw data and turn it into a visual artefact that will inform decision making.

During the implementation of WP3 a thorough stakeholders’ analysis has been performed including: i) the identification of the case study stakeholders groups, creating an inventory of organizations, institutions, etc. having some relationship with the case study; ii) the identification of the stakeholders’ interest and characteristics (This detailed information about each stakeholder can be found in NEWBITS D3.1);iii) and assessment of the stakeholders considering their importance and influence, based in the information gathered from each stakeholder. During the performed stakeholders’ analysis considering the result values of this evaluation, a visual diagram was created and the stakeholders had been classified in primary, secondary and tertiary stakeholders. One of the outcomes of the performed stakeholders analysis a mapping exercise has been undertaken characterising relations and dependences between stakeholders, and creating a visual diagram and explaining the interrelation between stakeholders as well as the value flows.

In the process of development, the proposed new business model of ITS and C-ITS applications and solutions in the framework of NEWBITS project, key components of business research is performed in WP3: Holistic Intelligence process. In D3.1 a thorough Market Research Analysis is performed while in D3.2 a benchmarking of ITS innovation diffusion and ITS production processes EU vs USA will be implemented. To get stakeholders and users feedback i.e. markets' feedback will be analysed in D3.3 Conjoint Analysis on case studies.

Based upon the outcomes of the previous synthesis section of this report, it is attempted to escalate the accumulated knowledge to fit with the descriptions of the selected case studies.

The **business ecosystems (BE)** notion appears well associated to the case studies. Battistella et al, 2013⁷⁷ mention “Business Ecosystems can be seen as complex adaptive systems (CAS): a system of multiple loops and chains, loops within loops, mutual crossfeed relationships connecting them, inhibitory connections, preferential reactions given different substrate concentrations” Accepting the above definition for BE, and applying it to the four case studies as examined entities with the work elaborated in WP2 and WP3 specific BE components have been already examined while the proposed tailored VNA and the mapping exercise of the relationships amongst the participants define the BE of each case study. Battistella et al, 2013⁷⁷ identifies the importance of the monitoring process for its ecosystem, both from a static and dynamic point of view, and analyse BEs by investigating how the relationships and the dynamics can potentially positively and/or negatively impact the businesses of the BE members. The work undergoing in NEWBITS project maps the respective case studies BE at a specific point of time. The importance of the dynamics of the BE and how are taken into consideration during the NEWBITS project are further elaborated in a following section of this report.

Based on the analysis of the stakeholders performed in WP3 for CS1 the main stakeholders are UAB Management (UAB MAN); UAB Mobility Unit (UAB MU); UAB Living Lab CORE (UAB CORE); UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit (UAB LOGA); Aslogic S.L.; FrontierCities; CRUE; Websays and the end users. The stakeholders in the D3.1 are categorised in the following groups: Cities: UAB Management; Transport authority: UAB Mobility Unit; Academia: UAB Living Lab CORE, UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit; ITS service providers: Aslogic S.L.; Funding body: FrontierCities; ITS associations: CRUE (Spanish Universities Association); Social media marketing companies: Websays; End users: Members of the university community (students, administrative staff, academic staff, other users accessing campus on periodic base). The stakeholders and the relations between them can be described as a Business Ecosystem. The multiple loops; mutual cross feed relationships and different substrate concentrations between the stakeholders, following the above definition, we can consider CS1 BE as a Complex adaptive System.

From the descriptions of the four (4) case studies each one can be considered as a network of stakeholders addressing a common issue through the development of a (C-) ITS solution / method / application. The network is defined by the nodes i.e. the participant actors, detailed mapped during the WP2 and WP3 and how are these nodes are connected, an exercise that will be implemented in D4.2 through the proposed tailored made VNA. The **Network Business Models** concept is considered very related to the analysis and the design of the new proposed business

model for (C-) ITS solutions. Libert et al, (2014) define a Business Model as the principal way an organization invests its capital to generate and capture value. During their research, forty years of financial data for the S&P 500 companies have been examined, and as a result they identified four types of Business Models: Asset Builders; Service Providers; Technology Creators; and Network Orchestrators. Towards the identification of the new BM in the framework of the NEWBITS project, the most interesting identified type of BM are the Network Orchestrators. The companies that apply / adopt this BM are creating a network in which all the participants interact and eventually have a specific proportion in the value creation. Examples of companies that are considered as network orchestrators include eBay, Red Hat, and Visa, Uber, TripAdvisor, and Alibaba. Unfortunately, from the research performed up to now in the framework of NEWBITS, it is still unclear if there is a network orchestrator in all the case studies, or the networks can be considered more distributed. The role of each of the stakeholders in each case study will be further defined and quantified during the performance of the proposed tailored made VNA. The premise is that each stakeholder has a particular business model in sight, that can be transformed in the context of the case study when all stakeholders behave effectively as network actors.

The four case studies are addressing specific issues and provide an ICT solution. The involvement of the stakeholders is identified in different stages of the solution development, and it can be said that the solutions are co-created. Case studies' stakeholders are exchanging information both for the development of the new (C-) ITS solution and for its effective operation. The time, magnitude and type of exchanged information is different per case study though it takes place in all of them. The information exchanged in most of the case studies takes the form of raw data exchange. For instance in CS3 a pilot application called "synchro modal container transport corridor Rotterdam-Limburg" is presented. Synchro modality refers to the possibility of choosing the most optimal transport modality at transshipment points. To allow for this, real-time information is needed on the transport chain. In the pilot project of CS3 a platform is developed to share real-time data on container transport from deep sea terminal Rotterdam to warehouses in Limburg (NL). Similarly, CS4 addresses the need to use experts' knowledge when analysing data to inform decision making in the railway industry. In particular, the case study uses data and experts knowledge to serve three overarching purposes within the British railway industry: Infrastructure management; Customer safety; Business performance.

The above characteristics are some of those that drive us to the conclusion that the examined case studies can be considered as service systems. The case studies are based upon the interactions between the participant stakeholders which is a very important characteristic of "**Smart Service Systems**".

The examined four case studies, although are utilising different ITS technologies and the derived final solution / service are different, share common characteristics. One of these characteristics is that three of them CS1, CS2, and CS3 are addressing issues in specific geographical regions and provide solutions for it. CS1 is focusing in the UAB campus, CS2 in the city of Verona and CS3 in a geographical corridor from the deep sea terminal of Rotterdam to warehouses in Limburg (NL). As it has been already mentioned in the previous sub-section the keys to **Industrial Symbiosis (I-S)** are collaboration and the synergistic possibilities offered by geographic proximity. IS can also be categorized conceptually as collective resource optimization based on

by-product exchanges and utility sharing among facilities. In an ideal setting, by-products and energy are exchanged by the actors of the system, thereby reducing the consumption of raw material and energy inputs and the generation of waste and emissions. In the examined case studies the concept is not to reduce the consumption of raw resources but are driven by the identified limitation of raw “resources”.

CS1 can be considered an appropriate example with a conceptual extension of the IS key concepts. In CS1 companies are not integrated in the network in the way that IS defines, at least at first understanding of it. The stakeholders are networked to deploy a sustainable intercity mobility solution to increase the average occupation and achieve a rational use of cars in a university environment with high levels of daily influx of private vehicles. In UAB campus (CS1) the parking slots are limited while the demand for them is increased. Hence, it can be argued that the addressed limited resource are the parking slots. The geographical proximity, which is another key concept / element of I-S is also a key characteristic of the solution analysed in this case study. Evolutionary approaches (like path dependency) to industrial symbiosis are found to be important in creating the level of cooperation needed for multi-party exchanges as the stakeholders participating in CS1. In IS the sharing among facilities is another key element, which in CS1 takes the form of car-pooling between the students.

In the city of Verona a system has been implemented to address heavy traffic and daily congestion. Thus, in CS2 the raw resource limitation is the capacity of the roads in the city of Verona to absorb the increased demand of the vehicles to move. This limitation is addressed by the network of actors engaged in CS2 using (C-) ITS components and applications to optimize how vehicles pass through the crossroads. According to Albino et al (2016), Industrial Symbiosis (IS) concerns the cooperative exchange of resources through business networks aimed at achieving at the same time economic, environmental, and social advantages (Industrial Symbiosis Networks-ISNs)⁷⁸. In CS2 the network of stakeholders manage to save both energy and emissions, avoiding any unnecessary acceleration or braking from the driver of the vehicle. The implemented solution in CS2 also addresses the very important societal challenge of road safety. One of the common resources used is radio frequencies through a bi-directional radio communication system between the traffic light control system and the equipped vehicles.

In CS3 the capacity of the “corridor”, is limited i.e. a resource limitation is identified. The increased demand to transport containers and the continue increase of the role of Rotterdam sea terminal; in the global transports drove the creation of this network of actors and made them to collaborate utilising state of the art ITS tools to enhance the knowledge or in a broader sense the intangible flow between them. CS3 is a collective resource optimisation based on information exchange and utility sharing facilities.

Different technologies are used in the case studies though most of them can be considered that they have elements that can categorise them into **Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS)**. Broy and Schmidt (2014) argue that many manufacturers will have to reinvent their innovation and development processes and take a user-centric engineering approach. This re-invention in the case studies is already taking place through the combination of different ITS technologies to provide solutions through a user-centric engineering approach. In CPS there are different

challenges and issues that have to be addressed. CS1 as an example address challenges of Global Information Systems (GIS) and Global Positioning Systems (GPS). The pilot application described in CS2 refers to a traffic management platform in the traffic management centre (TMC), where autonomous ITS systems and applications exchange data and are coordinated by a higher level subsystem. In the combination of the use of OBUs (On-Board Unit) to transmit data the application can be considered a highly demanded CPS. In CS3 the developed CPS require real-time information on the transport chain. The developed platform share real-time data on container transport from deep sea terminal Rotterdam to warehouses in Limburg. In CS4 a CPS is the key component to collect data, about the status of railway lines, gathered by the trains in a pilot line in the British Rail Network.

CPS are addressing very complex issues and are demanding raw computing power and accurate sensors. In combination with the demand for a greater capacity network infrastructure, to support the data collection may well become the theory backing up a new wave of computing. Therefore, CPS should be able to deliver new levels of performance and efficiency thanks to sophisticated control-computing co-design.

NEWBITS focuses on the challenges to support the adoption of ITS products and services by the market innovatively. This adoption is considered that can be achieved by the design of new business models for the provision of ITS services and solutions. **Service-dominant (S-D) logic** is a conceptual framework proposed by Lusch and Vargo (2004). S-D logic aims to explain value creation through exchange, among configurations of actors. It describes service as the core purpose of exchange and provides a theoretical understanding of how firms, customers and other market actors co-create value through their service interactions with each other.

The case studies address services, in which the value creation, differently conceptualised in each case study, is the fundamental basis of exchange. In at least the CS1 and CS2 can be justified as well that the value is co-created by the network stakeholders. The value is co-created by the service recipients, which are the service consumers/users, and the service providers as well. The identified stakeholders in each case study are not part of a vertical value chain but in different ways are exchanging their know-how, services, tools and resources to deliver value in a broader sense. This exchange can not be considered as outsourcing, since the relationship between them appears stronger and deeper. Lusch et al (2007) describe S-D logic as a collaboration between the firm (and relevant partners) and the customer allowing for a strategic orientation that informs the more tactical “Four Ps.” Products are viewed in terms of service flows, in which the service is provided directly or indirectly through an object; promotion is reoriented toward conversation and dialog with the customer; price is replaced with a values proposition created by both sides of the exchange; and place is supplanted with value networks and processes. In NEWBITS case studies the “products” are essentially considered as “service flows”; the “promotion” as an increase in awareness and intangible flow with the recipients; the “price” as a value proposition in different perspectives per case study and the “place”, despite being geographically focused as pilot applications, is considered more as a network and a process.

The literature review identified valuable information about **value networks**. As it is already presented one of the key notions in value networks is that value is created during the relation

between its members and not solely by the members as nodes. The importance of the relationship between the stakeholders is also identified in the descriptions and analysis of the case studies. The quantification of this value and the importance of each node in the emerged networks in each case study will be addressed by the proposed tailored made VNA.

The network of stakeholders in CS1 provide a very specific solution to the users. This solution includes a value proposition to the end consumer which are the users (students, academic-administrative personnel...) that are commuting with private cars in and out the UAB campus. The value proposed includes both the time that students are saving using the application but also the fact that they are going to find a place to park inside the campus. In CS1 emerged network, the focus is not set on each member but on the value created by the network itself, which is one of the characteristics that can define it as a value network.

CS2 refers to an C-ITS application implemented recently in the city of Verona. The developed ITS platform acquires all the traffic measures, and stores the information in a central system archive together with estimated statistical profiles such as traffic volumes, speed, etc. and traffic related data (e.g. signal plan, clearance capacity, turning proportions etc.). More than 150 intersections in Verona were connected with this platform. The intersections are the nodes of the of the infrastructure ICT network. In this report the value network that is examined is composed by the stakeholders identified in the CS. The importance of the co-operation, under a value network, between the municipality, equipment manufacturers, transport operators, ICT service providers and of course the end users is very clear for the successful operation of the C-ITS application. Each of the stakeholders have a different role in the network and adds value on it, both by their activities and services and by developing relationship among other stakeholders.

In CS3, one of the crucial success factors and operating requirement is the exchange of data and knowledge between the members. The exchanged information and data sets between the members of the network can be considered as intangible assets. The developed ICT platform can be considered the tool that supports the operation of the network, and the set of procedures that guarantee this exchange, the mechanism to support it. The network is creating value to all members through the exchange of this information and through the virtual relation between the members. The above key points justify that CS3 can be considered as a value network.

In CS4 the stakeholders co-operate and generate customer value (i.e. the train operating companies) and create network value by means of a specific service offering, valuable information for the predictive maintenance of British Railway lines through monitoring. The exchange of intangible assets between the CS4 stakeholders involved create extra value in the network.

2.3 Business Ecosystem Dynamics

Market uncertainties, fierce competition and constant improvement of stakeholder competencies in the field of ITS lead to new scenarios in which product and services must be redefined and improved constantly, having an impact on both the members and their relationships in the ecosystem.

The members of a Business Ecosystem need to watch and foresee what will happen in the near future considering the volatile and changeable context. Understanding the ecosystem means not only identifying the stakeholders and its relationships in a certain moment in time, but understanding how it evolves by monitoring evolutionary trends. In order to react on changes quickly and efficiently, a keystone member of the ecosystem must be able to foresee what will happen considering present member ITS competencies, and the very fact that ITS field is being performed in a changeable environment, introducing in this way uncertainties in the ecosystem dynamic evolution, and unfortunately introducing more difficulties in the decisions to be taken cooperatively by the ecosystem members.

It is well accepted that the behaviour of a business ecosystem can be described as complex adaptive system (CAS) which is characterized as a system of multiple loops and chains, loops within loops, mutual cross feed relationships connecting them, inhibitory connections, preferential reactions given different substrate concentrations. Unfortunately, the relationships connecting the ecosystem members cannot be always easily visualised as tangible values instead there are several intangible values with hidden dynamics that impact on the ecosystem behaviour and can determine its sustainability and the successful or failure of the ITS innovation.

Intangible values, usually are considered in the business ecosystem literature the non-financial resources that ecosystem members can draw upon to generate value. Consider for example ecosystem member's competence that can be used to improve knowledge products and services if trust between members is ensured in all the relationships. Informal exchanges are the key to create trust and open pathways for innovation and new ideas between the business ecosystem stakeholders.

The analysis of the dynamic value flows between BE stakeholders would support the better understanding of the evolution of the business model dynamics, which following can contribute to the identification at early stages of business shortages that would lead to a poor acceptability of the proposed ITS service/product or the failure of the full innovation process. In fact, the nature and effect of the dynamic interactions in a BE can have profound implications for organisational success and determines the speed of the ecosystem's evolution to keep it sparkling, offering plenty of opportunities for its members.

The dynamic nature of BE is considered as one of the pillars for adaptation not only to environmental and market uncertainties but also to the internal configuration to reach a stable structure with the right number of stakeholders necessary to be competitive with respect to other business ecosystems. By supporting and enhancing business ecosystem adaptation mechanisms it will be possible to identify those ecosystem parameter configurations under which the business ecosystem could be maintained and in consequence be sustainable.

The change, adaptation, and evolution dynamic mechanisms inherent to business ecosystems can cause uncertain ecosystem outcomes which are hard to predict and take time to materialise. Thus, a deep understanding of the ecosystem dynamics would contribute to design control policies and mitigation mechanisms to properly drive the ecosystem to successful scenarios, overcoming gaps in knowledge/ skills and gaining access to critical resources, including financial capital.

Systemic Business Dynamics

Systemic dynamics is a methodology for modelling complex dynamic systems which are usually characterised by feedback information loops between the contextual environment and from system behaviour. The first modelling formalism reported in the literature is the early Forrester work from Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in 1961. Forrester's work provided the basis for the evolution of different modelling formalisms, each one with particular characteristics but all of them supporting the analysis of feedback mechanisms.

Thus, as a previous task to choose the NEWBITS modelling formalism to specify the business ecosystem dynamics, it is important to identify the non-functional requirements that characterize the dynamics under study:

- Non – linearity: Accepting new stakeholders in the business ecosystem structure doesn't leads to proportional increments in the BE indicators.
- Non – predictability: A small change in a particular value flow between stakeholders can block or improve the valuable relationships between the stakeholders. Thus, a lack of trust at a certain life-cycle period of the BE can have negligible consequences or can even affect the sustainability of the full ecosystem.
- Interdependency: Key relationships between stakeholders can direct the business ecosystem from one dynamic state into another, which provides an opportunity to design flexible strategies to tackle unexpected events.
- Synergetic conduct: The right engagement of the stakeholders with complementary competencies on the service or product under study can generate better results than an outsourcing of some key competencies to external firms, or to a stakeholder that is not properly networked in the ecosystem. Since each firm in the ecosystem has his own targets, costs and benefits, decisions taken by each member should enable to create globally coherent behaviour patterns unconsciously out of local component interactions.
- Reversed connections: There is a cyclical process in which ecosystem stakeholders take decisions that result in some value flow changes, and value flow changes again influences on stakeholder decisions that will be made later heading the bE toward success or failure.
- Self organisation: A BE can be seen as an organized group of interacting firms working together for a purpose.

All these characteristics apparently makes the business ecosystems a very unstable system from the dynamic point of view, very sensitive to any change, however, the reality shows that the keystone role provides a robust mechanism to mitigate all those dynamics that could harm the ecosystem as a whole.

Systemic dynamics as a methodology used for a better understanding of the ecosystem behaviour supposes the construction of a simulation model of the ecosystem dynamics through a sequence of well accepted steps described in Table 2:

Steps	Description
1. Formulation of the problem	Definition of the problem and adjustment of the objectives.
2. Design of the conceptual model	Specification of the elements of the system and its interactions considering the objectives of the problem.
3. Data collection	Identification, collection and analysis of the necessary data for the study.
4. Construction of the model	Construction of the simulation model based on the conceptual model and the collected data.
5. Verification and validation	Verification that the behaviour of the model agrees with the conceptual model and the collected data, checking that the simulation model represents the real system.
6. Experimentation and analysis	Analysis of the simulation results for the purpose of detecting problems in the real system and recommending improvements.
7. Documentation	Providing documentation about the study that has been carried out.
8. Implementation	Putting the decisions taken with the support of the simulation study into practice.

Table 2: Development of a Simulation Model

The first 3 steps are very well supported in NEWBITS however a word of caution emerged in step 4 and 5 regarding the modelling approach to be used and its validation.

An important aspect that has been considered in NEWBITS to identify a modelling formalism that could support the specification of ecosystem members and its relationships is the use of *Continuous models* versus *discrete models*

Continuous models are characterized by presenting the ongoing evolution of the variables under study. In general, ordinary differential equations are used for modelling the evolution of variables over time, or partial differential equations are also used for modelling the evolution of the variables, but in terms of space.

Discrete event models are dynamic, stochastic and discrete, where the state variables change their value in non-periodic instants of time, without being governed by a clock. These instants correspond to the occurrence of an event. So, an event is defined as the instantaneous action that can change the state of a model.

Similarly, to the definition of continuous models, *discrete models* are characterized by discretely representing the evolution of the variables that describe the dynamics of interest.

It is important to bear in mind that, based on the above classification of models, it is possible to describe a continuous system by means of a discrete model and vice versa. The decision to use a continuous or discrete model depends on the particular objectives of each study and not so much on the characteristics of the model. Thus, for example, it is possible to find flow models describing the accounting of any firm in the organization while there are also models describing the value monetized by each firm at certain time periods, quantifying the value capture process at relevant milestones.

Thus, considering the importance to support a VNA adapted to C-ITS and ITS in NEWBITS, it has been chosen a discrete event approach in which the different pictures of evolution over time of the ecosystem through network analysis can help in this way in giving suggestions to business.

Another important modelling feature to be chosen in NEWBITS for the systemic business dynamic formalization of an ecosystem has been the abstraction level at which the actor behaviour and its relationships could be described.

- *Discrete Event*: A sequence of events that describe the evolution of a system regardless if they are computed by a deterministic or stochastic approach, consider the entities as passive elements with attached attributes that can only be updated by the functionalities specified in the formalized events.
- *Agent Based Models*: The behaviour of the system (i.e. its dynamics) cannot be formalized in an event or sequence of events, instead, its behaviour is obtained as results of the interaction between the system components, thus, the modeller just focus in the behavioural description of each actor and the different relationships between them.

Business Ecosystem Modeling

In NEWBITS, business ecosystems are considered from a socio-technological perspective in which control and observable variables coexist with influence variables that better supports behavioural dynamics subject to intangible values. Thus, instead of formalizing a set of events that could affect the dynamic behaviour of a business ecosystem it is recommended to describe the autonomous behaviour of ecosystem members as agents and try to obtain the ecosystem dynamic behaviour as results of the actors, each following its behavioural rules, living together in the same environment and formalizing the communication mechanism between each other and with the environment.

In Figure 1 Simulation model frameworks considering time evolution and abstraction level it is represented different modelling formalism considering the orthogonal classification features of time and abstraction level.

Figure 1 Simulation model frameworks considering time evolution and abstraction level

As it can be observed in the figure, Agent Based Models (ABM) are suitable to formalize any abstraction level dynamics, and the main work for the modeller is to choose the right abstraction level to support the analysis tasks, that in NEWBITS will be implemented in a modified VNA approach.

Among these dynamic modelling approaches, in NEWBITS it is proposed the use of Agent Based Modelling (ABM) because it supports different types of tangible and intangible relationships connecting the actors of the BE and in consequence provides an excellent quantitative analysis tool not just for business ecosystem strategies, also to predict the future behaviour of the BE and in consequence provides the basics to design mitigation mechanisms by suggesting new roles or changes in the stakeholders.

ABM allows a socio-technical modelling approach to search for explanatory insight into the collective behaviour of agents obeying simple rules. Agents are considered as autonomous entities that are able to perceive and act upon their environment. representing humans, systems, organizations, and any other entity that pursues a certain goal. In NEWBITS, agent entities are used to represent actors in the BE, reacting real world to the computational environment in which they are located, where this environment is a model of the real environment in which the BE

stakeholders operates. A quantitative analysis of the ABM would reveal BE behaviour emerging from the agent's collective actions and interactions.

The ABM representation fulfil the complexity of multi-loops in the business ecosystem since it can represent its dynamics:

- The aspects of human behaviours.
- The tangible and intangible values flowing between stakeholders.
- The business models that are applied by the involved actors.
- The interrelations amongst the involved actors.
- The description of the socio-economical environment.

Each component of the business ecosystem is represented by an individual agent, acting and interacting with other ecosystem members in a shared environment.

The main elements of the reference model will be:

- Agents, encompassing a possibly heterogeneous behavioural specification.
- Their environment, supplying agents their perceptions and enabling their actions.
- Mechanisms of interaction among agents: these mechanisms can either involve a direct exchange of information among the involved entities or an indirect one, realized through the possible perception by an agent of the effects of another agent's action.

A proper representation of agent actions must be given. Actions are the elements at the basis of agent behaviour, they can cause modifications in their environment or in other agents that constitutes the agent-based model.

Different modelling solutions can be provided in order to describe agents' actions, such as the following:

- The transformation of the global state of the business ecosystem;
- A local modification of the environment;
- A response to influences associated to agent perceptions;
- The execution of computing processes, carried out internally by an agent to elaborate perceived data and change its own state;

However, the agents' behavioural specification also includes the mechanisms effectively selecting the actions to be carried out, according to the perceptions and internal state of an agent.

The agent's environment, in the specific context of simulation, is typically responsible for managing the structure of the socio-technological arrangement of the overall ecosystem;

ABM Business Ecosystem in NEWBITS

The modelling target of a systemic ecosystem business dynamic in NEWBITS is the identification and description of the ecosystem stakeholders, its relationships together with decision rules and actions of the keystone in order to obtain global view of the ecosystem behaviour.

- Agents: In each case study, agents could be used to describe the ecosystem members.
- Behavioural rules: Each agent has a set of decision rules. We assume that agents' behaviour can be described by rules with which it can be computed the effects of receiving tangible or intangible values. In these rules, the positive or negative network externalities they experience can be incorporated. This means that an agent will look at other agents' status in making its own decisions.

Unfortunately, the extremely complex nature of such a business ecosystem makes it very hard to define any dynamics on the ecosystem level; there is an absolutely lack of knowledge for that. In order to formalize the behavioural rules, it will be considered the working knowledge of the relevant actors in each case study through different surveys and a workshop, trying to justify by means of how an action they take can influence an individual partner or customer. With this background, it should be possible to begin the dynamic modelling tasks by abstracting behavioural rules of individual companies, and defining relationships/interactions among them. Moreover, by modelling the individual companies as agents, it could be possible to observe the emergent behaviour taking place in the ecosystem.

Discretization at Business Ecosystem Milestones

Despite the benefits of ABM, it must be accepted that it has been applied only at research level in the field of business ecosystem providing incipient, probably because the extremely complex nature of business ecosystems makes it very hard to formulate by means of behavioural rules any dynamic of intangible value flows (consider for example trust, knowledge, comparable expectations) which are the essential ingredients at early stages of the BE creation to evolve towards more tangible values.

Although the modelling of BE by ABM would support the analysis of its behaviour, embedded as a network of relations between the stakeholders, there is a lack of control theory that could be applied to analyse and understand the feedback mechanisms of socio-technological systems to identify early signs to tackle the uncertainty both in the stakeholder relationships and the market environment. Furthermore, validating agent decision rules using historical and/or real-world data is not feasible since successful or failed business ecosystems can report only about one evolution and not how the ecosystem would behave in case of stakeholders would be taken other decisions and in consequence another network relationship would be achieved.

Thus, considering the problems of analysing internal business ecosystem dynamics and recognising that time is a fundamental variable that impact on the stakeholder's relationships and in consequence affects the ecosystem structure, in NEWBITS it is proposed to discretize the

ecosystem dynamics in a sequence of milestones which are dependent of each case study evolution and data that can be acquired.

The benefits of discretising the dynamic behaviour of the business ecosystem ABM model to the right milestones is that avoids the analysis of hidden interactions while focussing on a better understanding of key relationships to provide visibility to the intangible values that sustain the ecosystem behaviour.

By discretising the ecosystem dynamics to relevant milestones, the modelling results can be unfortunately biased due more subjective and less scientifically rigorous assessment of the ecosystem dynamics, but this risk, once identified can be properly managed with surveys and face to face validation methods during the foreseen case studies workshops. Thus, in NEWBITS, the first step to model the dynamics of the tangible and intangible value flows has been to collect the right knowledge by preparing a survey for the experts within the companies and engage them in a workshop to recognize how an action they take, can influence another ecosystem stakeholder, and formalize the stakeholder working knowledge in the ecosystem as a set of simple agent behavioural rules together with the relationships/interactions among them. With this approach we expect in NEWBITS to enhance the basic core of business ecosystem concept in which stakeholder's decisions are not taken in isolation, but instead they are influenced by the decisions of others ecosystem members.

It is proposed to identify ecosystem milestones when a relevant change in the ecosystem dynamics occurs. As a result of CS1 experience, it is suggested to monitor the following ecosystem attributes which somehow are the most frequent causes of a new ecosystem behaviour:

- A new pattern of relationship between BE members to better drive the dynamics to succeed with value creation purposes.
- A change in the member roles or in its attributes.
- A change in the reciprocity flow of values between partners

Furthermore, in CS1 despite the ecosystem is dynamic in terms of evolution phase (time) the members and its operating modes are quite stable, mainly because the supply side of the ecosystem is very well identified, the market size in which the ecosystem is operating is limited and because competences are very complementary and it has not been detected the need of an exit or entry of stakeholders unless there is a perfect substitute to fill the empty position or the entrant is merely replacing a leaving member.

The importance of ABM when applied to CAS is the possibility to analyse and predict tipping points at which a sudden shift to a contrasting dynamical regime may occur. In fact, it would be a robust mechanism to document for each CS business ecosystem in NEWBITS the early-warning signals that may indicate if a critical threshold is approaching. In the particular ecosystem model for case study 1, since it is quite stable and small scale ecosystem, we will try to identify qualitative indicators through the different pictures of evolution over time of the ecosystem at the proposed milestones.

3. Justification of the tailored VNA method

3.1 The “Bridging” section

In this section we present the validation of the tailored VNA method adopted in NEWBITS. This is the outcome of a process that leads to the justification of the adopted tailored made VNA methodology, starting from the findings of the literature review. The results of the literature review have been presented in Section 1. The literature review performed by a group of experts working in parallel. The review was focused on seven main areas which correspond to seven business modelling concepts.

A second strand of analysis was performed with a focus on the classification of NEWBITS Case Studies into the above concepts. With this effort we examined the degree of correlation between each Case Study to the reviewed business modelling concepts.

Finally, a third strand of work was implemented aiming to estimate the degree of adequacy and suitability of the proposed tailored made VNA methodology in order to track and capture the value creation and exchange aspects of the NEWBITS Case Studies. This work is referred in the text as the “Justification of the tailored made VNA”.

The combined outcome of the above three activities leads to the validation of the proposed tailored made VNA as an instrument capable of meeting the requirements of the NEWBITS case studies. At the same time the above process led to an improved determination and delimitation of the NEWBITS methods in the wider landscape of the examined concepts.

This process is depicted in Figure 6. The three activities referred above are converging in order to formulate the new business models for ITS/C-ITS, anticipated under the framework of NEWBITS.

Figure 2 Logical sequence from the literature review to justification of Network business models and tailored made VNA

The above process is considered as an incremental knowledge advancement procedure. The outcome of each strand of the analysis is consisted of content which leads, according to a step-by-step approach, towards a solid base for the justification of the methodology adopted for the formulation of the NEWBITS business models. The anticipated blocks of content (all focused towards NEWBITS Project and specifically WP4) are:

- Key elements of concepts
- What lessons learned per concepts
- What consideration to be taken into account

Figure 7 illustrates the above process and its outcomes, as an incremental knowledge advancement exercise.

Figure 3 Literature review: an incremental knowledge advancement exercise

The outcomes of the above procedure are presented in detail in the following sub-sections, per each examined concept.

Business Ecosystems

The business ecosystems are considered in the literature as sources of competitive advantage. Based on concepts from the value networks theory, business ecosystems are treated either as networks of interdependent stakeholders who evolve together and share the same fate, or as established value networks with fixed interconnected roles. In Europe the business ecosystems model is more flexible and dynamic, allowing even small firms to play key roles in the ecosystem, provided that they feature specific and unique capabilities. The literature converges to a common opinion stating that a business ecosystem should serve the strategic goal of co-evolution with buyers and governments to build a sustainable business ecosystem. The ultimate result anticipated for a business ecosystem is sustainable value creation that may last for large time periods, based on regeneration and self-adaptation abilities emerging from the networked nature of the ecosystem.

Due to the fact that business ecosystems are a perfect paradigm of complex adaptive systems, as they feature multiple loops and feedback paths between many interacting entities, it is imperative to establish a sound measurement approach based on quantitative data, to allow monitoring and assessing the performance of the ecosystem. This is a prerequisite that allows to optimize the rules governing the ecosystem. The complexity of business ecosystems suggests that the emergence and success of ecosystems is a dynamic process requiring a multifaceted responsiveness.

Many of the principles of business ecosystems are applicable to the NEWBITS Case Studies. The networks anticipated under the frame of the Case Studies will be dependent on the different resources possessed by their members. It is anticipated that, in these networks will coexist both competing and complementing functions. The networks to be formed for the Case Studies will be coordinated and orchestrated by a lead member entity. The NEWBITS Case Studies will involve a number of small firms that may play a key role in the respective ecosystems, based on their specific and unique capacities. The overall orientation of the NEWBITS Case Studies is to setup business ecosystems in the ITS/C-ITS sector, which will be able to adapt their operation under changing external conditions, through the initiation of new activities when needed, in order to maintain their sustainability through uninterrupted value-creation over time.

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge ecosystems are based on value chains where value creation flows from upstream to downstream players • The model of business ecosystem developed in Europe, is less structured and more dynamic • Firms in a restricted business ecosystem should consider coevolution with buyers and governments as a strategic action to build a sustainable business ecosystem. • The end-result of the process is a value-creating business ecosystem, which has the capacity to create value even for decades, adapt to ever-changing context by renewing itself, and initiate new value-creating activities in the future. • The business ecosystem stakeholders portray specific cooperative behaviour during the business ecosystem life cycle. • The capabilities of ecosystems define the service levels and societal gains. • The emergence and success of ecosystems is a dynamic process requiring a multifaceted responsiveness • Business Ecosystems can be seen as complex adaptive systems (CAS): a system of multiple loops and chains, loops within loops, mutual cross feed relationships connecting them, inhibitory connections, preferential reactions given different substrate concentrations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private financial agents play a central role in facilitating the transition from knowledge to business ecosystems. • Knowledge ecosystems are based on value chains where value creation flows from upstream to downstream players • This principle is supported by the theories of business networks, which suggest that: i) networks are dependent on the different resources possessed by their organizations ii) that relationships between organizations can be characterized by their competing or complementing offerings and iii) that network development is a purposeful activity coordinated by a focal firm • The end-result of the process is a value-creating business ecosystem, which has the capacity to create value even for decades, adapt to ever-changing context by renewing itself, and initiate new value-creating activities in the future. • The business ecosystem stakeholders portray specific cooperative behaviour during the business ecosystem life cycle. • The capabilities of ecosystems define the service levels and societal gains. • The emergence and success of ecosystems is a dynamic process requiring a multifaceted responsiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEWBITS CS are business networks dependent on the different resources possessed by their organizations ii) the relationships between stakeholders can be characterized by their competing or complementing offerings and iii) that network development is a purposeful activity coordinated by a focal firm. • Each CS can be considered a value-creating business ecosystem, which has the capacity to create value, adapt to ever-changing context by renewing itself, and initiate new value-creating activities in the future. • CS include small firms that have unique capabilities (offerings) can have a key role in each business ecosystem.

Table 3 Knowledge accumulation and filtering on business ecosystems

Network Business Models

Nowadays companies are struggling for continuous innovation in order to gain competitiveness. Towards this goal firms are reforming their business models. Networking is a concept that characterises our era and affects many aspects of life including the business and social domain. In terms of capabilities for innovation, the firms that participate in a network have significant advantages. It is widely recognized in the literature that a network-based business model offers significant boost to its member to innovate. For firms that are part of a network any incremental change in one partner’s tools, technologies, systems or products/services may have radical innovative effect in the entire network and to any particular member. Networked companies enjoy the benefits of a much stronger focus on joint innovation, which is boosted by the network effects. In such Network Business Models, changes and adaptations to the ever-changing external environment, are anticipated and welcome when there is a need to solve new and challenging problems. Thus today’s Network Business Models feature an intensively dynamic nature. In the literature have been identified four main types of Network Business Models: Asset Builders; Service Providers; Technology Creators; Network Orchestrators. Among them Network Orchestrators feature the most interesting and dynamic aspects.

The NEWBITS Case Studies consist of four groups of cooperating stakeholders that constitute representative examples of Network Business Models. Each one of the four case studies can be seen as a network of stakeholders addressing a common issue. Since all Case Studies are aiming to develop and offer innovative solutions and services, the concept of Network Business Models and the associated analysis strategy are considered very relevant to the NEWBITS Case Studies.

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A network-level BM is a powerful tool for individual companies to innovate with, particularly when the partners recognise that important competencies needed but not available in-house can be accessed through a partnership with other firms. • Compared to single-firm models, the network-level BM has a much stronger focus on the basics of how joint innovation can ultimately create new values accompanied by diminishing costs for the stakeholders involved. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Four types of BM identified currently: Asset Builders; Service Providers; Technology Creators; Network Orchestrators • Network Orchestrators. These companies create a network of peers in which the participants interact and share in the value creation. They may sell products or services, build relationships, share advice, give reviews, collaborate, co-create and more. Examples include eBay, Red Hat, and Visa, Uber, Tripadvisor, and Alibaba. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The justification of the existence of a NO in each CS would be achieved during the performed VNA. Few companies operate as Network Orchestrators. The (C-) ITS applications and solutions developed in the CS cover the requirements of today’s network-based BM • To become a NO and create more value and better performance, leaders must connect to and activate their networks, tapping into new sources of value, both tangible and intangible. The power of the networks of each CS is that their stakeholders are from different sectors –

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic business models are conceptualized as the emergent outcomes of pre-conceived network structures built through the development of routines that guide problem solving. • Three kinds of measurements that might influence the success of collaborative networks are explored in this paper: (1) Input to the collaboration, that is the contribution of each participant; (2) Mechanism of the collaboration, that is the health of the collaboration; (3) Output of the collaboration, that is the results of the collaboration activities 		<p>industries thus creating a new cross industry transformation.</p>
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Table 4 Knowledge accumulation and filtering on network business models

Smart service systems

In recent literature the term “service” is referred as the “provision of assistance and expertise through a provider–client interaction to create and capture value in business, education, government, and personal endeavours”. Service systems are described as configurations targeting to value co creation between people, technology, value propositions connecting internal and external service systems, and shared information. Smart Service Systems are integrated systems that interact in real time with their environment collect data, perform intelligent processing on the data and provide outputs in the form of interactive feedback, that is optimally adapted to fulfill the particular needs of the users in real time. Such systems have different variations based upon the level of autonomous decision making, that they can perform. Smart Service Systems are always associated to a digital solution. They may have a disruptive potential which depends on the characteristics of the digital solutions and the digital maturity level of the participating entities. The disruptive effect is related to the introduction of a totally new business model to accommodate the smart service provision. The challenge in order to introduce disruptive Smart Service Systems is to find appropriate business models and monetize value by analysing, visualising and transferring data into new service concepts.

In the framework of NEWBITS the four examined Case Studies refer to four systems of interconnected entities that exchange information and are targeted to the provision of optimal services, based on interaction to their environment, processing of collected data and responding in real time. The key feature of these systems is the intelligent interactions between the participant stakeholders. Due to the above facts we may conclude that, the main concepts of Smart Service Systems appear to be included in the four examined NEWBITS Case Studies. The concept of

Smart Service Systems should be taken into consideration in the design of the new business model for (C-) ITS applications.

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart service systems: allow real-time data collection, continuous communication and interactive feedback • Smart services vary on 1) level of autonomous decision making and 2) visibility and embeddedness in objects and customer lives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation of value: dependent on the value consumers see in smart services and in how much they value their own active participation. • Business models change from product-centric to solution-based • Value in use vs. value in exchange. Past models can be used to understand but not to estimate value/ A company's service must be completely different • Value is not what goes into goods and services, it is what customers get out of them; i.e. value emerges in the customers' space rather than in the producer's space • The logic of service is to support the customers' value-generating processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In CS1, CS2 and CS3 end-users / consumers becomes an active participant in the co-creation of value. do not draw value directly from the product /service itself; rather, by using, transforming, and consuming it, value in use is realised. • The and network of stakeholders in CSs as entities cannot deliver value, but only offer value propositions • All CSs to identify appropriate business models and monetize value should analyse, visualise and transfer data into their new service concepts. • All CSs offer Product–Service Systems (PSS) defined as a marketable set of products and services that are capable of jointly fulfilling customers' needs in an economical and sustainable manner

Table 5 Knowledge accumulation and filtering on smart service systems

Industrial symbiosis

Industrial Symbiosis (I-S) is an interesting cooperative model in the emerging field of industrial ecology. Industrial Symbiosis is defined as “physical exchange of materials, energy, water, and/or by-products to promote resource efficiency between traditionally separate industries with the intent of promoting collective competitive advantage”. Industrial Symbiosis innovatively strengthens the synergies between industries and optimizes the utilization of resources. This optimisation of resources is achieved by the exchange of by-products and energy between the actors. A key characteristic of I-S is the geographic proximity between actors which enhances collaboration and possibilities for synergies. The feature of geographic proximity usually creates positive impact at a local or at the regional level.

In NEWBITS the four case studies involve networks of stakeholders which provide mainly intangible services. The case studies bear the main characteristics of Industrial Symbiosis, namely, collaboration based on the synergistic possibilities offered by geographic proximity.

Indeed, the case studies are location-based focus. Although the examined case studies are utilising different (C-) ITS technologies and offer different final solutions and services, they share common characteristics. Three of them (CS1, C2, and CS3) are operating in specific geographical regions and provide solutions within them. CS1 is focusing in the UAB campus, CS2 in the city of Verona and CS3 in a geographical corridor from the deep-sea terminal of Rotterdam to warehouses in Limburg (NL). These are good examples of networks of actors that follow the Industrial Symbiosis concept.

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial symbiosis (IS) concerns the cooperative exchange of resources through business networks aimed at achieving at the same time economic, environmental, and social advantages (Mirata, 2004). • Self-organized ISNs are framed as Complex adaptive systems (CASs) (Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012). • The idea of industrial and regional symbiosis innovatively strengthen the synergies between industries optimize the utilization of resources and to make full use of the social function of industries to urban communities through the provision of living necessity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through industrial symbiosis, firms are interested to achieve competitive advantage coming from lower production costs and revenue increase. Therefore, the first requirement for the establishment of a symbiotic relationship is its economic sustainability for all the firms involved. IS-based business oriented to product generation. • Industrial symbiosis engages traditionally separate industries in a collective approach to competitive advantage involving physical exchange of materials, energy, water, and/or by-products. The keys to industrial symbiosis are collaboration and the synergistic possibilities offered by geographic proximity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CS1, CS2, and CS3 explore and take advantage of the synergistic opportunities offered by geographic proximity of a diverse set of business. • In the three CS the types of businesses that join symbiotic clusters appear that address behavioural hurdles, clarify the role of intermediaries, and the longevity of such cooperative approaches

Table 6 Knowledge accumulation and filtering on industrial symbiosis

Cyber-Physical Systems

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) are considered as a critical pillar of the so called fourth industrial revolution. Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) incorporate both ICT infrastructure and software (the Cyber part) and hardware devices such as sensors and actuators together with human users (the Physical part). The two components are fused into a unified system that should perform in a reliable, secure and fault tolerant manner in real time. CPS are intelligent and adaptive systems capable to adapt in a sophisticated and smart way to fulfil varying and changing user needs within an ever-changing environment. It is recognised that the approach to modelling and designing

cyber-physical systems is to “cyberize the physical” (CTP), which means building software abstractions around physical subsystems. The need for networking and interoperability is a main feature of CPS. Such systems may reach their full value only when interconnected to a network infrastructure. The development of a CPS-operated environment requires also high performance and interoperable dynamic web-based and cloud-based services that will interact securely in real time with numerous and different networked devices. This raises the need for data integration. CPS provide a natural framework to address the challenges of the transportation sector, since they integrate the physical, cyber, and human factors in a single framework. For the C-ITS platforms, the need for data integration is even more intense. The importance of an Integrated Information Platform (IIP) for ITS, which processes various data from different traffic data sources located in various traffic management systems is imperative.

Although in the NEWBITS Case Studies a spectrum of different technologies are used, most case studies can be considered that they have elements which categorise them into Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS). The concept of Cyber-Physical Systems is more relevant to two out of four Case Studies, namely CS1: “University VAOPoint Mobility” and CS2: “C-ITS system to manage the drivers’ behavior crossing traffic lights intersections”. All typical requirements for CPS are present in both cases: multiple sources of data, intelligent and adaptive feedback to the real world (which includes large numbers of human users), all in a secure, reliable and robust way in real time.

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyber-physical systems will achieve full value only when they are integrated into a network infrastructure. Connecting most mechanical devices to a supporting infrastructure is fairly straightforward, but orchestrating dynamic Web- or cloud-based services for numerous networked devices will be a major challenge. • Connecting most mechanical devices to a supporting infrastructure is fairly straightforward, but orchestrating dynamic Web- or cloud-based services for numerous networked devices will be a major challenge. • Cyber-physical systems may well become the theory backing up a new wave of computing. Cyber-physical systems actively engage with the real world in real time and expend real energy. This requires a new understanding of computing as a physical act. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) provide a natural framework to address the challenges of the transportation sector, since they integrate the physical, cyber, and human factors in a single framework. It is important to obtain an integrated perspective of the physical and cyber-imposed challenges so that practical solutions that will realize the vision of ITS can be conceived • One challenge is learning how to live with networks’ limitations. While small-scale systems can use specialized real-time networks, national-scale systems will inevitably rely on the Internet for part of their operation. We need to understand what parts of a real-time, closed-loop system can be put on Internet protocol networks and what parts cannot. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The solutions provided by all the CS include some form of cyber-physical systems (CPS). From the CS analysis demand for new functionality features multiply in the developed CPS • All CS utilise a kind of an Integrated Information Platform (TIP) for (C-) ITS, which processes various data from different traffic data sources located in various traffic management systems. • The developed platforms serve as a bridge of data share and exchange among different application systems and data sources, which provides traffic management decision-making support, information service function etc. • Real-timeliness and reliability of information dissemination via V2V and V2I communication is a hard problem due to multiple challenges.

Table 7 Knowledge accumulation and filtering and filtering on cyber physical system

Service Dominant Logic

Service-dominant (S-D) logic is a conceptual framework that aims to explain value creation as the outcome of exchanges, among various configurations of actors. It describes service as the core purpose of exchange. S-D logic offers a means for theoretical understanding of how customers, firms and other market actors co-create value through their service interactions. A central issue in the literature of S-D logic is the distinction between “operand” vs “operant” resources. In the conventional goods-centric approach, the consumer was seen as an operand resource – a resource to be acted on. In S-D logic, there is a shift from the goods-centric view to a service-centric view and a shift from operand resources to operant resources.

In the NEWBITS Case Studies (CS) the concept of service as the fundamental basis of exchange, is dominant. The Case Studies foresee complex interactions between the players. The identified stakeholders in each case study are not part of a vertical value chain but in different ways are exchanging their know-how, services, tools and resources to deliver value in a broader sense. The Case Studies will use recent developments in ICT to interconnect large number of stakeholders and users into complex constellations that operate within a rapidly changing environment. This implies that CS feature multi-actor interactions and long-term relationships which are key issues in the concept of “value-in-context”, one of the pillars of S-D logic. The idea of a concept that interprets the operation of the Case Studies ecosystems, as a world dominated by service exchanges, suggests that S-D logic represents an appropriate framework to analyse the anticipated exchanges, since they are all service-critical.

The case studies address services, in the domain of logistics. Logistics, as a domain characterized by frequently changing service offerings, provides a context which fits to and may gain from the S-D logic perspective. In addition, logistics is also an important context because of the increasing importance placed on logistics service as a competitive tool. The context of logistics services is dynamic and continually changing. Value cannot be created unilaterally in such dynamic contexts. Further, value creation requires a combination of resources. In this context, the case studies will demonstrate value propositions based on the combined resources. The S-D logic perspective suggests that a firm must focus on employing the customer as a resource contributing to the creation of value that in effect makes the customer a co-creator of value. In the above dynamic and changing environment, S-D logic, can support, the issues related to the concept of “co-creation” of value in an optimal way.

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Dominant (S-D) Logic advocates viewing the customer as an operant resource – a resource that is capable of acting on other resources, a collaborative partner who co-creates value with the firm and promotes a “market with” philosophy. • S-D logic inverts the role of goods and service by making service super ordinant to goods. In S-D logic, service can be provided directly to another entity or network or through goods-appliances. • An S-D orientation represents a set of strategic capabilities that enable an organization to co-create value in service exchanges with what the S-D logic literature calls “value network partners,” such as customers, intermediaries, suppliers, or employees. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In Service Dominant Logic is important to recognize that there are two components of value co-creation: “co-creation of value” and “co-production”. “Co-creation of value” represents a rather drastic departure from Goods Dominant logic, which views value as something that is added to products in the production process and at point of exchange is captured in value-in-exchange (i.e. price). S-D logic argues that value can only be created with and determined by the user in the ‘consumption’ process and through use or what is referred to as value-in-use. • Service Dominant logic views marketing as social and economic processes, in which the concept of interaction is central. It embraces the idea that value creation is a process of integrating and transforming resources, which requires interaction and implies networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S-D logic designates the value concept as value-in-context. All CS fulfil the key dimensions of value-in-context which are: (1) multi-actor interactions (dyads, triads, networks), (2) value co-creation, and (3) long term relationship-value over time. • In all CS value is not created solely by the firm, but created with collaboration of the customers during their usage of products and interactions with different actors. • The role of each CS is to propose a value proposition via resources such as goods and services, and it is the customer who creates the value through a process over time.
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Table 8 Knowledge accumulation and filtering on service dominant logic

Value Networks

In recent years, economy is getting increasingly connected, as main industries like telecommunications, defense and aeronautics are more and more run by networks of organizations. The traditional concepts about value creation through linear models are no longer applicable. Products and services become dematerialized and the value chain itself is no longer having a physical dimension. The participating organizations need to collaborate with each other and constantly reconfigure their offering, positioning and relationships, in order to remain competitive and relevant in the market.

The concept of Value Networks (VN) was introduced in the innovation management literature as an approach aiming to understand the above developments and provide models for them. A value network is “a dynamic network of actors working together to generate customer value and network value by means of a specific service offering, in which tangible and intangible value is exchanged between the actors involved”. The value network has a purpose, which is to satisfy the value proposition to the end consumer. Value networks define the value created between the participating businesses and their clients or customers, and between the clients/customers themselves. Under this frame of thought, firms are considered as intermediaries that bring together customer while the linkage of customers in value networks create value. A major novelty of Value Networks is that intellectual capital and intangibles are introduced as a form of value

which is equally significant to tangible products. In the context of Value Networks, the technology is seen primarily as a medium for enhancing relationships in space and time, while the mechanisms creating knowledge value include: exchanges of strategic information, planning knowledge, technical know-how, collaborative design, policy development, etc., which flow around and support the core product and service value chain.

The Value Networks approach can be applied on multiple levels as it exhibits a high degree of tailoring capabilities. The VN concepts are relevant to NEWBITS both at a macro-level (ITS and C-ITS context and market) and a meso-level (the Case Studies). In the NEWBITS Case Studies the value is created during the relation between its members and not solely by the members as nodes, a fact that is aligned to one of the key notions in value networks. The NEWBITS Case Studies foresee the exchange of data and information between the members of the network. These exchanged information blocks are considered as intangible assets. The network is creating value by its existence to all members through the exchange of this information and through the relation between the members. The focus is not set on each member but on the value created by the network itself. The importance of the relationship between the stakeholders is clearly identified in the descriptions and analysis of the Case Studies. Each of the four networks of stakeholders in the four CS provide a very specific solution to the users. Each offered solution includes a value proposition to the end consumer. The above key points are perfectly aligned to the main aspects of Value Networks, a fact demonstrating that it is advisable to consider and analyse the NEWBITS Case Studies as value networks.

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A value network is defined as ‘The collection of upstream suppliers, downstream channels to market, and ancillary providers that support a common business model within an industry. When would-be disruptors enter into existing value networks, they must adapt their business models to conform to the value network and therefore fail at disruption because they become co-opted’ • Value networks refer to businesses that can be modelled as such, and define the value created between those businesses and their clients or customers, and between the clients/customers themselves. Firms are considered as intermediaries that bring together customers. Members need to complement each other. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value networks are important because in recent years we have made enormous process in terms of business productivity, but unfortunately a lot of our human interactions are in a way devalued, not given the same kind of consideration as business transactions, so we have this sort of disconnect between the two worlds of human interactions on the one hand, and business transactions on the other. • Traditional thinking about value creation has shifted from the linear model of the industrial age production to the new enterprise model of the value network, the value web or the value cluster. Its novelty lies in that it introduces intellectual capital and intangibles in business models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the value networks in the CSs, the role of knowledge value and intangible value exchange is equally important to tangible deliverables. • From the description of the CSs knowledge value include: exchanges of strategic information, planning knowledge, technical know-how, collaborative design, policy development, etc, which flow around and support the core product and service value chain • In the CS, the new (C-) ITS are only the pipelines for knowledge and value exchange. The exchange is what is really important. • Value Networks as a model of inter-organizational exchanges is an attempt to address the increasing intricateness of inter-firm

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value networks create value by linking customers. In value networks technology is used primarily as medium for enhancing relationships in space and time. The primary activities taking place in value networks include i. network promotion and contract management, ii. service provisioning and iii. infrastructure operation. Interactions take place simultaneously, not sequentially or cyclically. Activities are pooled and preferably reciprocal. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any organization can be understood as a value network. 	<p>relationships, pushed by a more and more connected economy.</p>
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Table 9 Knowledge accumulation and filtering on value networks

3.2 Proposed tailored made VNA

Value network analysis offers a way to model, analyse, evaluate and improve the capability of a business to convert both tangible and intangible assets into other forms of negotiable value, and to realise greater value for itself, as it is described by Allee (2008)⁷⁹. Underlying this approach is an understanding that intangible, but nonetheless strong and dynamic relationships, and the intangible assets that make up and have an impact on those relationships, are the foundation of any successful business endeavour. Indeed, the future success of a company or organisation as a whole depends on how efficiently a company can convert one form of value into another.

According to Allee (2008)⁷⁹, networks and roles are considered as value conversion mechanisms: Because the network is the primary economic mechanism for value conversion, network analysis can be used to describe the value creation dynamics of work groups, organisations, business webs, and purposeful networks engaging in both tangible and intangible value exchanges to support the achievement of specific outcomes and to generate economic and social good (MacCauley, 1963⁸⁰; Granovetter and Swedberg, 2001⁸¹; Allee, 2002⁸², 2003⁸³). The network is a value conversion mechanism that achieves not only positive goods and outcomes, but nefarious and negatives ones as well, according to the values and intent of those who serve the network. Creating value from intangibles: A transaction occurs when a deliverable originated by one role is conveyed to and received by another. Two or more reciprocal transactions are an exchange. Once an exchange has been negotiated, both parties can be held accountable for the effective execution of any transaction either originates. Value conversion: Participants in a value network, either individually or collectively, utilize their tangible and intangible asset base by assuming or creating roles that convert those assets into more negotiable forms of value that can be delivered to other roles through the execution of a transaction. In turn, the value of deliverables received is realized by participants when they convert them into gains or improvements in tangible or intangible assets.

Once all of the critical roles, value exchanges and transactions have been identified then it is possible to do full value network analysis. Value creation analysis looks at how each role adds

value to the network. Value creation analysis is basically an expanded cost/benefit analysis, with a focus on asset utilization. Value creation analysis explores five dimensions of value creation. 1) Asset utilization; 2) Value Conversion; 3) Value enhancements; 4) Recipient perceived value and 5) Social Value. Value network analysis can provide a systematic way for approaching the dynamics of intangible value realization, interconvertability, conversion, and creation. The key to understanding the knowledge economy lies in not only understanding intangibles as assets, but in coming to terms with how they are set into motion in unique configurations of relationships, interactions, and resources in value conversion networks.

The proposed tailored made VNA methodology, by ORTELIO, in the scope of NEWBITS, will build upon the outcomes of the stakeholder analysis performed in the deliverable D3.1 Market research⁸⁴ analysis and build-up on the results from D2.3 Case study taxonomy⁸⁵. In a first level, the following suggested grouping (below) will be aligned with stakeholder definition to be implemented in D3.1. The following Figure 4 Tailored VNA method blocks visualise the key conceptual blocks that will form the tailored made VNA.

Definition of the network and its actors	Stakeholders Interaction	Types of interaction	Mapping value flows	Crafting value propositions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. National Government; 2. ITS service providers; 3. European Commission; 4. International Partners (outside the EU); 5. Regulatory bodies; 6. Universities/Research Institutes; 7. OEMs; 8. Transport operators; 9. Automotive suppliers; 10. Public Authorities (another level to government i.e. infrastructure managers) 11. Users (focus on the needs of users) 12. Specialised Media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition, • Role, • Input, • Output 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science Knowledge regarding C-ITS and ITS systems • Scientific knowledge are distributed to various levels of the government • Science knowledge regarding mobile and business ecosystems; Science knowledge regarding new tools and applications; Science knowledge regarding satellite systems; and Science knowledge regarding cyber-physical systems; others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the highest value-producing interactions between the most important stakeholders at each case study; • Map value flows identifying interactions and major relationships between actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through collective ideation workshops

Figure 4 Tailored VNA method blocks

As it is shown in the above Figure 4 Tailored VNA method blocks the following key elements of VNA are addressed: (1) Exchange analysis – Attempting to identify the overall pattern of exchanges and value creation in the networks as a whole and how are they converting value; (2) Impact analysis – Identifying the impact of each value input on the roles involved in terms of value realization; (3) Value creation analysis – Pointing best ways to create, extend, and leverage value, either through adding value, extending value to other roles, or converting one type of value to another.

There are four stages in the proposed VNA, as it is shown in Figure 5 Methodological Stages of the Value Network Analysis. In the first stage as input will be taken into consideration the outcomes of WP2 the definition of the four (4) case studies and the identified networks. Each case study includes a number of actors. Aligned with the analysis performed in WP3 the roles, interactions and interactions types are identified in Stage 2. After describing the networks to be examined in stage 3 the Value Flows will be mapped. The whole process is proposed to include with stage 4 Validation and Ideation on crafting value propositions for each case study. According to the proposed methodology a co-creation based approach is recommend for the implementation of Stage 4.

Figure 5 Methodological Stages of the Value Network Analysis

For each of the four case studies the proposed tailored made VNA will be formalised to cover the specific requirements of each of them. Additionally, to the required modifications is proposed, based upon the analysis in Section 2.2 Business Ecosystem Dynamics, to introduce a dynamic element to the VNA via establishing a life-cycle monitoring for the business ecosystem in CS1. Specifically, for CS1 ORT, envisage three cycles/phases: Cycle 1: starting-up; Cycle 2: growing; and Cycle 3: maturing of the BE. For each of the cycles specific value flows will be proposed and evaluated by the stakeholders. Based on the theoretical analysis, it is considered that the evolution of the BE in CS1 as a result of new scientific discoveries, is expected to be justified, which is expected to lead to possible adaptation of roles, functions of actors/stakeholders or even to the exit/entry of some actors.

3.3 Justification of tailored made VNA

Based upon the extensive literature review performed in this report and the escalation of the examined knowledge blocks is considered justified that the four CS can be considered as Network Business models. Further, as documented in detail in section 3.1 above, the four CS feature a series of key dimensions of Value Networks, such as: dynamic networks of actors, value from intangible assets (exchanged information blocks), value proposition to the end customer, networks creating value by their existence to all members (value created during the relation between the members). The above findings correspond to the main aspects of Value Networks. Thus, it is recommended to consider the NEWBITS Case Studies as Value Networks, and to analyse them accordingly using an appropriate VNA methodology.

The tool for analysing the NEWBITS Case Studies is a tailor made VNA method proposed by ORTELIO, which is developed to fulfil the specific requirements of NEWBITS. This VNA method is described in detail in previous section 3.2. The proposed tailored made VNA, and its application performed in D4.2 is considered that will provide the NEWBITS consortium with valuable information about each case study NBM. The value flows, the stakeholders' roles / importance as outcomes of the proposed tailored made VNA, are considered key elements for the successful definition of the new business model for ITS. The following Table 8 summarises how each CS fits to each knowledge block, and if can they can be described by a NBM. The last row displays that the proposed tailored made VNA is justified for the analysis of all the four case studies.

	CS1	CS2	CS3	CS4
Business Ecosystems	☒	☒	☒	☒
Network Business Model	☒	☒	☒	☒
Smart service systems	☒	☒	☒	☒
Industrial symbiosis	☒	☒	☒	

Cyber-Physical Systems	☒	☒		☒
Service Dominant Logic	☒	☒	☒	☒
Value Networks	☒	☒	☒	☒
Network BM	☒	☒	☒	☒
Tailored VNA	☒	☒	☒	☒

Table 10 Summary of knowledge blocks and CS fitting

The proposed tailored made VNA will evolve through discrete and traceable blocks starting from the definition of the actors and concluding with the definition of value propositions. The procedure includes five steps:

1. Definition of the actors and their networks
2. Definition of interactions between stakeholders
3. Finalization of the types of interactions
4. Identification/mapping of value flows
5. Build value propositions

The above blocks build a lean approach that will lead to new working and efficient business models in the ITS domain. This approach is a systematic and structured way to reach the value propositions for the value networks to be created under the NEWBITS framework. We may state that all blocks are required for an efficient outcome of this effort. The above blocks could be partially implemented concurrently (for example blocks no 2 in parallel with block no 3).

The above approach offers the possibility to incorporate quantitative data and thus to exploit the predictive power of quantitative models. The tailored VNA method will include the required analysis effort which includes three types of analysis: i) Exchange analysis, ii) Impact analysis and iii) Value creation analysis.

The proposed tailored VNA methodology will use in an optimal way the results of NEWBITS produced so far, namely the outcomes of WP2 (D2.3) and WP3 (D3.1). These will form the basis to start the above procedure as they will become the input for the first block (Definition of the actors and their networks).

The proposed methodology will use the views of the potential actors and incorporate them to the new business models in a way that maximises the anticipated growth of value. This is due to the fact that these actors will have the possibility to express their expectations and concerns in the frame of the foreseen collective ideation workshops. The workshops are part of the work in the

last of the above blocks (Build value propositions) and they constitute the co-creation component in the formulation of the new business models. The participation of the potential actors in the workshops will ensure that the new models will evolve “naturally” in the sense that will fulfill the real expectations of all participants, an asset that reinforces the sustainability of the business constellations anticipated in the Case Studies.

The NEWBITS Case Studies although belonging in the same business context (ITS domain), feature significant variations. They vary in the modalities, the geographic extend, the operational focus, etc. The variations of CS ensure the wide coverage of NEWBITS that addresses many different aspects of the ITS domain. The proposed VNA methodology consisted of the above five blocks may serve all four Case Studies despite their differences. For each CS the method will be further tailored and formalized to capture all specific requirements set by each CS.

We may conclude that the proposed tailored VNA methodology may cover the needs for all four value networks anticipated in the frame of the four Case Studies. The proposed method includes the necessary steps in order to conclude to sound value propositions. In this sense it is a complete methodology. At the same it is a lean methodology since it includes only the necessary elements to reach sound value propositions. The proposed method is appropriate in order to fulfil the NEWBITS requirements, since it will utilize previous findings and outcomes of performed project activities. The method includes also the co-creation activities anticipated in the frame of the workshops. The combination of project results exploitation with the co-creation activities, guarantees that the method will track and assimilate all specific requirements of NEWBITS regarding the formulation of new business models in ITS domain based on VNA on the value networks foreseen in the Case Studies.

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